

D5.2 WILSON ontologies evaluation – Month 18

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This deliverable describes in brief detail ontologies that are available for use in the WILSON project, focusing on building- and district-context. This includes the adoption rates for these ontologies and potential gaps in these ontologies for their application in semantic local and federated district Digital Twins within the WILSON framework.	

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

Acronym	Full Form
ADE	Application Domain Extension
AECO	Architecture, Engineering, Construction and Operations
API	Application Programming Interface
BIM	Building Information Model
BMS	Building Management System
BOT	Building Topology Ontology
CEN	European Committee for Standardisation
DT	Digital Twin
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
gRPC	Google Remote Procedure Call
GIS	Geographical Information Systems
HVAC	Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning
LD	Linked Data
LBD	Linked Building Data
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
IDS	International Data Space
IDSA	International Data Spaces Association
IFC	Industry Foundation Classes
IoT	Internet of Things
ISO	International Organisation for Standardization
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
JWT	JSON Web Token
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
OWL	Web Ontology Language
RAM	Reference Architecture Model
PDH	Personalised Data Hub
RDF	Resource Description Framework
REST	Representational State Transfer
SAREF	Smart Applications REFerence
SCADA	Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition
SDO	Standardisation Development Organisation
SPARQL	SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language
SSN	Semantic Sensor Network
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
VPN	Virtual Private Network
XML	eXtensible Markup Language
XSD	XML schema Definition
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The objective of this report is to provide **a comprehensive analysis of ontology frameworks and ongoing standardisation initiatives** relevant to the data categories that are handled in the WILSON research project. This comprehensive ontology evaluation thus establishes the semantic foundations that enable interoperability, data exchange, and integration across the WILSON project's ecosystem of tools and applications.

This report first **surveys existing ontology frameworks**, with a particular focus on both energy-related and non-energy-related use cases (Section 3). An overview is provided of ontologies in the built environment, including material- and product-level ontologies, systems- and subsystems-level ontologies, building-level ontologies, and district-level ontologies. The survey and report evaluate their adoption, maturity, and alignment with European and international standards, while identifying gaps and overlaps that may pose challenges for large-scale deployment. Furthermore, the document outlines the selection of existing ontologies (see Section 3.6) relevant to achieving the WILSON goals. This list of ontologies follows the baseline for further development and implementations in the WILSON project. Collectively, the findings of this section (gaps and challenges) are furthermore directly connected to WILSON's vision of creating harmonised data models that can support diverse applications such as energy efficiency, building lifecycle management, and predictive maintenance. The current report also documents, in Section 4, the relation of ontology development to ongoing **standardisation initiatives**, including the European Committee for Standardisation (CEN), International Organisation for Standardisation (ISO), and European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI), as well as domain-specific efforts such as buildingSMART International, the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C). These standardisation bodies support in varying degrees the standardisation of linked data vocabularies (or ontologies) as well as sectoral data spaces. An overview of their work is presented in the report, which ensures that the WILSON framework is consistent with recognised standard practices and can be positioned for broad adoption (see Section 4.5). An additional smaller contribution of this report is the introduction of the **Vocabulary Hub** concept (Section 5), which is an optional component that can be used in the WILSON Data Spaces infrastructure, but is also of value in the creation of Personalised Building Data Hubs (PDHs). The Vocabulary Hub serves as a reference mechanism that provides access to relevant ontologies and controlled vocabularies, as documented in previous sections. An overview is presented of how this Vocabulary Hub can be implemented.

The methods used to achieve the above results include a literature review, comparative analysis of ontologies and standardisation efforts, expert consultation, and alignment workshops with stakeholders from the WILSON project. This evaluation process has been iterative and informs the further refinement of semantic models in and outside the research project. This report should thus be considered a foundational part for semantic integration in WILSON. Its outputs contribute to other research, including the definition of PDHs, the design of Data Spaces, and data integration workflows in general. By establishing clear guidelines for ontology adoption, standardisation alignment, and the implementation of the Vocabulary Hub, this report positions WILSON to deliver trusted, interoperable, and future-proof Digital Twin solutions.

2. INTRODUCTION

This Section establishes the main objectives of this report, elaborates the concepts used throughout, discusses their interrelations, and sets the scene for more detailed exploration of the ontologies for the built environment that can be used in the WILSON project. The objective of this work is to create a reference source of information that allows for functional data exchange across multiple systems, scales, and use cases, addressing the current fragmentation of information across BIM, IoT sensors, Building Management Systems (BMSs), and other sources. This work provides the necessary technical ontology overview for effective data exchange among stakeholders, as well as alignment with international standards. It evaluates existing ontologies and makes them available into the WILSON ecosystem of tools, particularly the Data Space and the Personalised (Building) Data Hubs (PDHs).

The rest of this Section is structured as follows: Section 2.1 introduces the key definitions that will be used consistently throughout the report. Section 2.2 sets out the main objectives, clarifying the purpose and expected outcomes of this work. Section 2.3 discusses the interrelations with other components, highlighting dependencies and the contribution of this work to the broader project. Section 2.4 explains the methodology used to analyse ontologies, detailing the criteria and approach. An ontology survey is presented in Section 2.5. Finally, Section 2.6 outlines the structure of the report, showing how the content is organised across the subsequent sections.

2.1. Definitions

This Report concerns the ontologies used for creating and enhancing interoperability and data exchange in the built environment. This section briefly describes important concepts and key terms.

The **built environment (BE)** refers to all human-made structures, such as buildings, infrastructure, and urban systems [1]. It has a significant impact on global energy consumption and carbon emissions, making it a priority area for sustainability initiatives. This sector's digital transformation leverages technologies such as Building Information Modelling (BIM), the Internet of Things (IoT), Geospatial Information Systems (GIS) and Semantic Web standards to improve the design, construction, operation, and end-of-life processes.

A **Digital Twin (DT)** is a dynamic virtual model of a physical entity, system, or process that allows for real-time and synchronised monitoring, simulation, prediction, and optimisation [2]. IoT sensors, BIM models, and semantic data models enable continuous data exchange between the physical and virtual worlds, which is required for Digital Twins to function. Digital Twins are used in the built environment to help with lifecycle management, energy efficiency, maintenance planning, and resilience assessments.

Interoperability is important to the WILSON project, ensuring that data from diverse sources such as BIM models, IoT sensors, BMS, and urban databases can be exchanged and used effectively across different systems and scales. This goes beyond technical compatibility to

include semantic interoperability, achieved using ontologies that provide shared vocabularies and align with established standards detailed in this Report.

An **ontology** is a formal, structured representation of knowledge in a specific domain [3]. It is typically made up of entities (classes), attributes, and relationships that allow for semantic reasoning and system interoperability. In the context of Digital Twin technologies for the built environment, ontologies provide a standardised framework for digitally representing physical assets, their properties, behaviours, and interactions with other systems [1]. Ontologies are classified according to their scope and purpose, such as domain ontologies (e.g., Web Ontology Language (OWL) version of the Industry Foundation Classes: ifcOWL, BRICK for building systems, etc.), and foundational ontologies (e.g., DOLCE) that define general concepts applicable across domains.

2.2. Main objectives

This Report addresses several core objectives related to the use of ontologies in the built environment and Digital Twin technologies, with a focus on defining the relevant ontologies to be (re)used in the WILSON project. The primary objectives include:

1. Analysis of Existing Ontologies

This objective involves a comprehensive review and **comparative analysis** of existing ontologies relevant to the BE and DT technologies. The analysis aims to identify ontologies that enable semantic modelling of built assets, materials, systems, and performance indicators. Key ontologies considered include IFC, Building Topology Ontology (BOT), BRICK, Smart Applications REFERENCE Ontology (SAREF), GeoSPARQL, Haystack, and Semantic Sensor Network Ontology (SSN). The evaluation assesses their expressiveness, interoperability, adoption rates, and suitability for both centralised and federated Digital Twin implementations.

2. Adoption of Ontologies in energy and non-energy use cases

Ontologies must be evaluated not only theoretically, but also in terms of their practical application to real-world use cases. This report investigates how **ontologies** can be used for both **energy-related use cases**, such as smart energy management, Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning (HVAC) optimisation, demand-side response, and occupant comfort assessment, as well as **non-energy use cases**, including fire safety planning, structural health monitoring, circular economy and facility maintenance. Special emphasis is placed on how these ontologies support semantic data enrichment, integration with IoT devices, and alignment with existing data formats and protocols.

3. Integration into the WILSON framework

Within the WILSON framework, ontologies play an important role in enabling **semantic interoperability** between different systems and data sources. While most of these ontologies are generally available through regular web technologies (dereferenceable Uniform Resource Identifiers (URIs)), they are additionally made available in so-called **vocabulary hubs** in the WILSON project. Vocabulary Hubs are standard components in the IDSA Reference Architecture Model 4 (RAM4) of the IDSA Data Spaces, yet ontologies

(or vocabularies) are also used in the PDHs in WILSON. At the time of writing, the IDSA RAM4 architecture is in the process of being superseded by the IDSA RAM5 architecture, and it is expected that the Vocabulary Hub will remain to play an important role in the RAM5 architecture.

4. Standardization Efforts

Standardisation is important to ensuring widespread adoption of ontologies across platforms, projects and stakeholders. This report helps advance standardisation efforts by **relying on existing standards** and **supporting efforts from recognised bodies** such as the International Organisation for Standardisation (ISO), the European Committee for Standardisation (CEN), the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C), and industry consortia such as buildingSMART and GAIA-X. WILSON's ontology choices are specifically aligned with emerging standards such as ISO 23247-1 (Digital Twin overview and general principles), ISO 19650 (Information Management using BIM), ASHRAE Standard 223P (Designation and Classification of Semantic Tags for Building Data), and OPC UA (Unified Architecture). The goal is to promote harmonisation, enhance data exchange and automation, reduce errors and fragmentation, and support long-term sustainability through governance frameworks and community-driven development practises.

2.3. Relations with other components of the WILSON project

This report is closely connected with several other components of the WILSON project:

- **Baseline assessment and performance framework:** The use and business cases defined in *WILSON use and business cases definition* provide input on energy and non-energy scenarios, guiding the selection and development of relevant ontologies. Tools to be developed in response to the requirements listed in *Baseline assessment and performance framework*, will need suitable ontologies to support their data input and functioning.
- **Semantic and federated Digital Twins at local and district levels:** *WILSON ontologies evaluation* provides the vocabulary definitions, ontology selection, and interoperability strategies that form the semantic foundation for the WILSON ecosystem of tools. Particularly, the ontologies can be used to create the Vocabulary Hub as listed in *Data Space: architecture definition and infrastructure setup*.
- **Data interoperability for data mesh enabled Digital Twins:** The semantic models and metadata schemas (ontologies) selected in this *report* feed directly into the development of Personalised Data Hubs (PDHs), ensuring consistent data enrichment and contextualization.
- **Digital Twins enabled lifecycle data solutions for energy uses:** The ontologies and semantic structures developed in *WILSON ontologies evaluation* support the integration of BMS and other monitoring systems (*Interface for Asset Management Systems, BMS and Digital Logbook*) by providing a standardised framework for data interpretation. The programming interfaces will output data based on the ontologies selected in *WILSON ontologies evaluation*.
- **Integration of technologies and preparation for pilots:** This *report* underpins pilot site integration by enabling consistent semantic representation of data, which is critical for validation, interoperability testing, and achieving *Integration of*

technologies and preparation for large-scale pilots. The tooling developed in *Integration of technologies and preparation for large-scale pilots* can make use of data that follows the ontological structure selected in this deliverable.

2.4. Ontology analysis methodology

It is important to indicate that, as part of this WILSON project and this Report, it is not expected that a new ontology needs to be created. As such, the aim is to reuse existing ontologies as much as possible. **In other words, no single “WILSON ontology” is assumed.** The main reason for that is the intent to follow best practices for ontology reuse. Naturally, the latter does not imply that specific extensions should not or will not be developed in case specific concepts needed in WILSON are not covered by existing ontologies. At the time of writing, there are many ontologies available, covering a large share of the information in the BE domain. It is widely recognised that multiple ontologies are available, and that creating a new ontology is usually only needed in rare cases. Hence, this work will primarily focus on reviewing existing ontologies, to be able to **identify and select the set of ontologies that will be (re-)used and supported in the WILSON project.** Additionally, the document considers to what extent such ontologies may need to be updated or extended, ideally in alignment with standardisation efforts, which are also addressed in the same Report.

Thus, several existing ontologies are analysed in this Report using a structured **Ontology Analysis Methodology**. This methodology establishes comprehensive criteria for ontology reusability assessment within WILSON, specifically addressing WILSON project requirements. The evaluation framework integrates FAIR principles, modularity requirements, web accessibility standards, alignment capabilities, and quality assessment metrics. This method is based on the work documented in [6].

Applying this methodology involves systematic ontology catalogue analysis using established criteria to identify optimal ontology combinations for WILSON use case implementation. The methodology emphasizes practical reusability and proves added value of ontologies through their successful use in related studies. In future work, practical usability will be further demonstrated through comprehensive case studies and validation scenarios in the WILSON demonstrator cases. This focus on practical usability ensures that the selected ontologies will effectively support WILSON's innovative approach to building and energy management while maintaining compatibility with broader data-ecosystem requirements.

The main criteria for analysis in the Ontology Analysis Methodology include:

- **Federated Data Space Reality:** Real-world Digital Twins involve distributed, heterogeneous data sources (e.g., buildings, energy networks, etc.) with diverse semantics and formats. The WILSON solutions aim for a federated data handling approach in response. Hence, the selected ontologies need to support such federated data architecture with a multitude of data sources as well as end-user tools.

- **Reuse, Not Reinvention:** Instead of reinventing, the current work aims to primarily reuse ontologies that have proven added value. Leveraging high-quality ontologies (versus custom ad-hoc vocabularies) ensures evolution, maintenance, and alignment with standards, thereby saving resources. As mentioned above, ontology reuse is also one of the most fundamental best practices highlighted by the W3C, which is the appropriate approach given the large number of ontologies available in the domain.
- **Modularity:** In line with the first criterion listed above, ontologies with a higher level of modularity are given priority. Highly modular ontologies ensure that they can be flexibly used and interchanged in combination with other ontologies. This ensures strong technical and organisational flexibility and alignment. As such, ontologies can represent the complexity of Digital Twins and can easily be combined and extended with other ontologies to respond to future scenarios.
- **Web-ready:** Given that the WILSON ecosystem is a web-native system, web-readiness is an important criterion. Ontologies for the WILSON solutions need to be available in web-friendly formats, including OWL and its serializations (RDF/XML, TTL), XML schemas, JSON schemas, or similar.
- **FAIR Principles:** Making ontologies Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable enables open innovation and semantic automation. Data spaces (e.g., IDSA, GAIA-X, REFORMERS) directly require these features for secure, scalable federation.

2.5. Ontology survey

Annex 1 presents a survey designed to collect and analyse the ontologies used by WILSON partners. In the current phase, the survey was conducted within the WILSON consortium. However, the responses were limited and not sufficiently detailed or statistically relevant to support a comprehensive analysis. Therefore, the survey will be expanded and conducted again in future research. The upcoming round will target a broader audience, including additional stakeholders and technical experts, to gather more representative and actionable input. The objective is to identify overlaps, gaps, and alignment opportunities across the ontologies in use, ensuring better interoperability within the WILSON framework.

Furthermore, as indicated before, the ontology selection will be based on the user requirements and data needs for the tools under development in future work, since those are the requirements and tools that these ontologies need to be support. Practical usability of the considered ontologies is to be evaluated in consideration of those tools, by checking to what extent such data from the WILSON demonstrator sites can be represented using the selected ontologies.

2.6. Report outline

The structure of this report is organised as follows:

- **Section 1** provides the executive summary.

- **Section 2** introduces background, objectives, and definitions. It also presents the goals and scope of standardisation efforts, the ontology survey and methodology, and the report outline.
- **Section 3** reviews relevant ontologies across multiple levels, from materials and products to building systems, buildings, and finally districts and cities.
- **Section 4** discusses standardisation efforts related to BIM, IoT, and semantic data exchange.
- **Section 5** presents the WILSON Vocabulary Hub, including its purpose, publication process, and methods for accessing and using ontologies. Its relation to the WILSON Data Space and the PDH is briefly outlined.
- **Section 6** summarises the main contributions of this Report and identifies areas for future improvement.
- The cited references and supporting documentation of this Report are provided in the References and Annex sections.

3. ONTOLOGY REVIEW

As indicated above, ontologies play an important role in the WILSON project. This Section first provides an overview of established ontologies relevant to the built environment and Digital Twin technologies (Section 3.1). Sections 3.2 to 3.5 provide a more detailed evaluation of the selected ontologies. Namely, Section 3.2 examines material- and product-level ontologies, Section 3.3 investigates ontologies for building systems and subsystems, Section 3.4 focuses on building-level ontologies, and, lastly, Section 3.5 extends the ontology overview to district-level ontologies. Section 3.6 presents a summary of the primary ontologies used in WILSON, as well as important features and challenges related to their (re)use.

3.1. Overview of Built Environment ontologies with relevance to WILSON

As indicated, the goal of this work and this project is **not to define a new WILSON ontology** but rather enable reuse and extension of existing ontologies. Before analysing the available ontologies in detail, the following section provides a summary of the technical foundations. Furthermore, the resulting overview of available ontologies also includes the reasons for selecting some specific ontologies over others.

3.1.1. Brief technical foundation

This report relies on the below definition for **an ontology**.

Definition: An Ontology

An **ontology** is a **structured, explicit and formal representation of knowledge within a specific domain**, defining concepts, relationships, and rules that enable consistent understanding and exchange of information between systems in a way that is both machine-interpretable and human-understandable [3].

Technically, given the above definition, an ontology does not need to be represented in one or the other language, except that this language needs to be structured and explicit, and adhering to a ‘form’. Several languages belong to that category, including XML and JSON, which can be argued to follow that definition. All in all, the data model itself (e.g., IFC, BRICK, CityGML) is more important as an ontology than the question in which language it is encoded. Nevertheless, the most common understanding in the literature points to an ontology being typically encoded using the Resource Description Framework (RDF) and the **Web Ontology Language (OWL)**. The below sections of this Report will thus focus mostly on OWL ontologies, but ontologies encoded using other formalisms will also be considered. The main definitions for RDF, OWL, and URIs are presented below, while Annex 2 provides an overview of tools that can be used to work with ontologies.

Definition: RDF, OWL, and URIs

The **Resource Description Framework (RDF)** provides the data model for representing information as subject–predicate–object triples. Additionally, the **Web Ontology Language (OWL)** adds logical semantics, which allows for

logical inference (reasoning). Each concept and relationship is assigned a **Uniform Resource Identifier (URI)** to make it a distinct resource on the Web, and these URIs can be accessed or referenced using the Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP).

This technical basis ensures that information described in different systems can be connected, queried, and understood in a shared and consistent way. As such, ontologies enable data interoperability and linking between heterogeneous data sources. In the built environment, such data typically come from BIM, BMS, GIS, and IoT platforms [4] [5].

Historically, early efforts in the development of ontologies in the built environment focused on standardising general **building data, product data and geometry** in an exhaustive manner, while more recent applications incorporate operational information, energy systems, sustainability indicators, and occupant behaviour, also in a more modular fashion. **Infrastructure** (i.e., bridges, tunnels, roads) concepts are also increasingly often represented using web-ready OWL ontologies and RDF graphs. Today, ontologies are regularly used in several **Digital Twins and smart building initiatives**, enabling data integration and improved decision-making throughout the building life cycle [5].

3.1.2. The coverage of an ontology

There are now **hundreds of built environment-related ontologies** [6], with more domain ontologies being developed and used. Although many of them are openly available and reusable, a single ontology is rarely sufficient in its entirety for any other project for a number of reasons outlined below.

Ontologies typically **differ in purpose and coverage** because they are created by various research and development groups, which have tailored their ontologies to meet the specific needs and scope of their projects. Several ontologies often **overlap**, yet the overlap is near to always small and on a rather generic level (e.g. `building owl:sameAs building`). Despite the fact that some general resources such as *building* or *sensor* appear in several ontologies, these ontologies often differ significantly in their granularity and conceptual modelling. Each ontology has been developed to serve specific project objectives, that often lead to distinct relationships, hierarchies, and properties. As a result, even when ontologies share overlapping terms (e.g., concepts such as *building*, *space*, or *sensor*), these similarities often remain at a high level and do not extend to having similar relationships, hierarchies, and properties. Hence, in practice, combinations of concepts from **several ontologies are typically used together**, to be able to represent the different dimensions and characteristics of an object or a building (e.g., topology, geometry, product, sensor data).

It is also worth noting that some ontologies have evolved from an ontology cluster. For example, the IOT ontology is part of the COGITO ontology cluster, thus, it is extremely well-aligned with other ontologies from the same cluster. Yet, some other standalone ontologies may have received broader recognition and adoption due to their precedence or supportive standardisation efforts, such as SOSA and IFC. This leads to our conclusion that there is no single, authoritative, "main" ontology that can be universally applied to relevant WILSON use cases such as energy monitoring and optimisation (for which sensors and IoT data are

needed). The **decision to adopt one ontology rather than another**, even where both contain a sensor class, **is in the hands of the implementers**, who must determine *which classes and relationships*, rather than *which ontology*, best fit their technical and contextual requirements.

3.1.3. Ontologies to evaluate

The ontologies in this report are classified at the **material and product levels, systems and subsystems levels, building level, and district level**. In the forthcoming Sections, each ontology is evaluated based on its semantic expressiveness, alignment with WILSON data categories, interoperability potential, and relevance to both energy and non-energy use cases. A summary of the ontologies studied across different data categories within the WILSON framework is provided in Table 1. The WILSON Data Categories are detailed in Data handling, management and protection. The ontologies have been selected based on the User Requirements and Data Requirements, as well as extensive user studies and a survey among project participants (see Section 2.5).

Table 1. Overview of ontologies based on WILSON Data Categories

WILSON Data Categories		Relevant Ontologies
	Sensor data	BRICK, Haystack, Smart Applications REference Ontology (SAREF), Semantic Sensor Network (SSN), Sensor, Observation, Sample, Actuator (SOSA), COGITO IoT Ontology (IOT)
	Building systems data	BRICK, Industry Foundation Classes (IFC), Building Topology Ontology (BOT), Digital Twin Construction Ontology (DTC), RealEstateCore (REC)
	Energy management data	BRICK, SAREF, Haystack, SOSA/SSN, REC
	User specific data	Occupant Feedback Ontology (OFO), REC
	Maintenance & operations data	BRICK, REC
	Point cloud model data	Ontology for Managing Geometry (OMG), File Ontology for Geometry formats (FOG), BOT, Built Element Ontology (BEO), IFC
	BIM data	IFC, BOT, REC, BEO, Material Properties Ontology (MAT), Building Product Ontology (BPO)
	External data	GeoSPARQL, OntoCityGML, CityRDF
	Environmental data	Environmental Impact Ontology (ENV-O)

	Financial/economic data	Economic Ontology (ECO), Costing Ontology (COST-O)
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The ontologies in Table 1 are further reviewed in detail in the remainder of Section 3. Besides generally reviewing selected ontologies, a portfolio overview of each ontology is provided as a table. These tables include name, description, BE-OLS Evaluation Rating as a spider chart [6], relevant WILSON Data Category, and alignment with standards. The BE-OLS ontology evaluation graph assesses an ontology’s maturity and reusability across three key axes of Connectivity, Accessibility, and Reuse & Documentation [6]. The ENV-O, ECO and COST-O ontologies for environmental data and financial/economic data are not included in this more detailed review, since they are currently not listed as targeted demonstrator data. These ontologies may be revisited in the future.

Some of the ontologies reviewed in this section are revisited in Local and Federated district-level Digital Twins. This Report presents the minimum WILSON Digital Twin’s federated architecture with a core layer as well as pilot-specific extensions meant to capture specific use case requirements. This supports the general idea and notion here **that no single ontology can fully represent the conceptual depth and breadth required for WILSON’s core or extension needs**. For WILSON, this means that several of these ontologies may hold relevance, as the project covers diverse data categories and use cases. The use of diverse and well-aligned ontologies can enhance data integration and exchange across the WILSON ecosystem. Accordingly, this report reviews and identifies a set of ontologies most suitable to support WILSON’s current and anticipated future needs. As indicated above, the ontologies presented in this report are selected while evaluating their usefulness and coverage in relation to the data categories. The purpose of this review is to map the landscape of relevant ontologies and assess their suitability, rather than prescribe a definitive set for adoption. In principle, all listed ontologies can be equally and similarly supported.

The true value of the reviewed ontologies in this report will become evident through their practical application and integration within the WILSON’s dataspace, PDH, and Digital Twins, rather than through theoretical comparison alone. Hence, this constitutes future work. Furthermore, the WILSON Data Space does not prescribe or control which exact ontology is used by individual data providers or data consumers, as this depends very much on the nature of the intended exchanges.

3.1.4. Selection of ontologies

From an early review, ontologies such as **IFC, BOT, BRICK, SAREF, SSN/SOSA, REC, and (Onto)CityGML** stand out as comprehensive frameworks with broad domain coverage that are well-suited for semantic building and urban Digital Twins within federated data spaces like the WILSON project. These ontologies exhibit strong adherence to the **FAIR principles** - ensuring their findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability - and are widely supported by active communities, extensive documentation, and modular architectures facilitating scalable and flexible adoption. Furthermore, these ontologies have established alignment and mapping relationships with each other, enabling integration across

disparate data sources and domains crucial for multi-source decentralised data management and comprehensive Digital Twin operations. Their maturity, openness, and **embedding within standardisation frameworks** make them foundational pillars for semantic interoperability in the AECO industry. Ontologies like Haystack and BPO prove valuable in more specialised contexts such as building automation metadata and building product representation.

Emerging and research-driven ontologies address important yet specialised or emerging domains. Because of their developmental status, these ontologies often lack the full maturity, standardisation, documentation, or community support needed for sustainable, large-scale deployment and therefore may require ongoing refinement, standardisation, and alignment effort before full implementation in WILSON can be properly considered. More specifically, they need to be published and available on the Web so they can be reused.

In general, the **more detailed review of ontologies** (Section 3.2-3.5) shows that the ontologies listed in Table 2.

Table 2. Overview of selected ontologies in the WILSON project.

Ontology	Domain Coverage	Alignment & Mapping	Documentation & Community
IFC	BIM/geometry	BOT, BRICK, SAREF	Extensive, maintained
BOT	Topology	IFC, BRICK	Active, lightweight
BRICK	Sensors/BAS	Haystack, IFC	ASHRAE, Growing, docs
SAREF (+extensions)	IoT/energy	SSN, BRICK, IFC	ETSI, standard
SSN/SOSA	Sensors	SAREF, BRICK	W3C, mature
Haystack	BAS/metadata	BRICK	Wide adoption, docs
REC	Asset/space	BRICK, IFC	Active, open source
BPO	Products	Schema.org, others	Research, mature
BEO	Built elements	IFC, BOT	Wide adoption, mature
OFO	Feedback	BOP	Research, some docs
OntoCityGML	3D city model	IFC	OGC, mature
GeoSPARQL	Geospatial	CityGML	OGC, mature
CityRDF	3D city model	CityGML	OGC, under development
FOG	BIM/Geometry	OMG	Wide adoption, mature
OMG	BIM/Geometry	BOT	Wide adoption, mature
IOT	IoT/Sensors	SAREF	Research, mature
DTC	Asset/Process	BEO, BOT, GeoSPARQL	Research, mature
MAT	BIM/materials	SAREF	Research, mature

3.2. Material- & Product-Level Ontologies

Ontologies at the material and product level represent building materials, components, and products, as well as their physical, chemical, and environmental properties. These

ontologies are essential for applications such as Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), sustainable material selection, performance-driven design, and end-of-life and circular decision makings.

3.2.1. Material Properties Ontology

The Material Properties Ontology (MAT) is part of the BIMERR ontology Family, a project that received funding from Horizon 2020 (Grant Agreement No. 820621). MAT (details in Table 3) provides a vocabulary to describe building elements, their material composition, and the properties and measurements needed in building renovation scenarios. This ontology reuses some concepts from IFC and SAREF and is thus aligned with them. The main use case of this ontology (in line with the BIMERR project) is renovation scenarios. As such, in terms of describing materials and compositions, as well as renovation scenarios, MAT is of use for the WILSON project.

Table 3. Ontology Profile – MPO

Category	Details	
Description	MAT ontology supports modelling and exchange of information about material types or compositions	<p>BE-OLS Ontology Evaluation Graph</p>
Namespace	https://bimerr.iot.linkeddata.es/def/material-properties/	
General Use Cases	Sustainable material selection, life cycle assessment, maintenance planning, digital product passports, Material Science, Renovation, Digital Twins, Building products, manufacturers, material composition	
Dependencies	SAREF, BUILDING (BIMERR Building Ontology)	
WILSON Relevance	Essential for energy and non-energy use cases involving material descriptions or performance metrics	
WILSON Data Category	BIM data	

3.2.2. Building Product Ontology

The Building Product Ontology (BPO) is a structured representation of a product, including technical specifications, functional roles, and relationships with other elements (details in Table 4). BPO allows for detailed descriptions of the constituent elements of a mono- or multi-part products, how the parts are related to each other and how they are aligned with building typology [7]. In WILSON, BPO can be used to support semantic modelling and enrichment of products to be exchanged between suppliers, contractors, and facility managers, particularly in procurement, maintenance and reuse workflows.

Table 4. Ontology Profile – BPO

Category	Details	
Description	BPO Ontology represent construction products, and components. It semantically describes how parts and a whole are interconnected. Materials and geometries are not included in this ontology.	<p>BE-OLS Ontology Evaluation Graph</p>
Namespace	https://w3id.org/bpo#	
General Use Cases	Sustainable material selection, life cycle assessment, maintenance planning, digital product passports, Product Detailing, Material Science, LCA, Facility Management, Renovation, Digital Twins, Building products, manufacturers, warranties, material composition, performance metrics	
Dependencies	Smart Energy Aware Systems (SEAS), Quantities, Units, Dimensions, and Types Ontology (QUDT)	
WILSON Relevance	Essential for energy and non-energy use cases involving product descriptions, material performance, sustainability, and lifecycle tracking; supports semantic enrichment of BIM and maintenance data	
WILSON Data Category	Building Systems Data, BIM Data	

3.2.3. Smart Applications Reference Ontology – Building devices (SAREF4BLDG)

SAREF4BLDG ontology, sometimes written as S4BLDG, is an extension of the SAREF ontology family. SAREF4BLDG is specifically designed for smart buildings and energy-efficient systems by ETSI (details in Table 5). While primarily intended for building-level semantic representations, SAREF4BLDG includes definitions of devices and products, particularly those involved in energy consumption and control systems. SAREF4BLDG supports the modelling of devices such as sensors, actuators, and smart appliances. As such, it is ideal for integration into energy management systems and IoT-based monitoring platforms. It is also compatible with BRICK and NGS-ILD. Its lightweight structure and compatibility with NGS-ILD make it an excellent choice for use in real-time data contexts within WILSON.

Table 5. Ontology Profile – SAREF4BLDG

Property	Value	
Description	Extension of the SAREF ontology for smart buildings, enabling semantic representation of building systems, appliances, and energy-related devices. Supports modelling of sensors, actuators, and control	

	functions in energy-efficient environments.	BE-OLS Ontology Evaluation Graph
Namespace	https://w3id.org/def/saref4bldg	
General Use Cases	Energy efficiency monitoring, demand response, smart metering, interoperability with BMS and IoT platforms, Smart building devices, energy consumption monitoring, HVAC, lighting, and appliance control, Smart Buildings, Energy Management, IoT, Digital Twins	
Dependencies	SAREF	
WILSON Relevance	Key for energy use cases; supports semantic enrichment of IoT data; integrates with Data Space connectors and Vocabulary Hub	
WILSON Data Category	Sensor Data, Building Systems Data, Energy Management Data	

3.2.4. Built Element Ontology

The Built Element Ontology (BEO) (details in Table 6) is developed to define the built environment and building elements based on instances of `IfcBuiltElement` from IFC 4.3.2.0 (ISO 16739-1:2024). As such, this ontology is structured as a pure taxonomy: it has primarily classes as well as `subClassOf` relationships defining the hierarchical subsumption relations. Only few data properties are included. BEO is widely used and well-aligned with IFC. It is developed through a new `IFCExpress2BEO` custom converter. The Built Element Ontology is the latest updated version of the Building Element Ontology, which had mostly focused on building elements. The newest version focuses not only on buildings but on many built environment elements, for example also for bridges.

Table 6. Ontology Profile – BEO

Property	Value	
Description	BEO aims to provide a straightforward way for semantically describing various built environment elements. It does not go into material level and remains at element or product level.	<p>BE-OLS Ontology Evaluation Graph</p>
Namespace	https://cramonell.github.io/beo/actual/index-en.html	
General Use Cases	Describing building and built environment elements: from walls to truss, to elevators and doors	
Dependencies	Stand-alone. It has no dependencies with other domain ontologies. While not reusing any concepts from other ontologies, it is used by many other ontologies.	
WILSON Relevance	Used for semantically defining the built environment elements and create a foundation for minimal building Digital Twins in various WILSON pilots	
WILSON Data Category	BIM data, Point cloud model data	

3.3. Systems- & Subsystems-Level Ontologies

Ontologies at the systems- and subsystems-level represent Mechanical, Electrical, and Plumbing (MEP) systems, Building Automation Systems (BAS), Building Management Systems (BMS), and sensor networks. These ontologies are critical for enabling seamless exchange of information and interoperability between heterogeneous systems, as well as real-time monitoring, diagnostics, and predictive maintenance.

3.3.1. BRICK

The BRICK ontology (details in Table 7) is a widely used schema for describing building systems, sensors, and points of interest. BRICK, designed specifically for smart buildings and building automation, provides a modular and extensible framework that enables users to define relationships between HVAC zones, sensors, actuators, and control strategies. Using BRICK, semantic inference can be done for anomaly detection, fault diagnosis, and optimisation algorithms. Brick has alignment with BOT and REC according to the publicly available documentation. Within WILSON, BRICK will serve as a foundational ontology for energy-related use cases that require real-time sensor data integration and analytics.

Table 7. Ontology Profile – BRICK Schema

Category	Details	
Description	A formal ontology for representing building systems, sensors, and control points in smart buildings. Designed for semantic modelling of HVAC, lighting, and energy management systems.	<p>BE-OLS Ontology Evaluation Graph</p>
Reference	https://brickschema.org/resources/	
General Use Cases	Real-time sensor data integration, HVAC optimization, fault detection, energy benchmarking, Smart Buildings, Building Automation Systems, IoT, Energy Management, Building systems, equipment, sensors, zones, and control logic	
Dependencies	SOSA, REC, SAREF, IFC, QUDT	
WILSON Relevance	Core ontology for energy-related use cases; integrates with Vocabulary Hub and Data Space connectors	
WILSON Data Space	Energy Management Systems, Building Systems Data, Maintenance & Operations Data, Sensor Data	

3.3.2. Haystack

Haystack (details in Table 8) is a tagging-based ontology designed for modelling metadata in BMS/BAS. This means that Haystack is not OWL/RDF native but can be mapped to RDF/OWL via HSK-ONT or Haystack-RDF mappings. Thus, a downside of Haystack is its

limited native support for reasoning engines and plain Semantic Web technologies without RDF conversion.

Haystack describes entities and attributes using a hierarchical tag system rather than formal OWL semantics. This approach makes implementation and adoption easier in existing BAS environments, especially where legacy systems dominate. However, its lack of formal semantics limits advanced reasoning and integration capabilities. It also supports JSON, Zinc, and CSV formats. Despite this, Haystack continues to be an asset for retrofitting projects and initial data harmonisation efforts at WILSON.

Table 8. Ontology Profile – Haystack

Category	Details
Description	A tagging-based ontology for modelling metadata in building automation systems (BAS) and IoT devices. Haystack uses a hierarchical, human-readable tagging system to describe equipment, points, and relationships. It is widely used for retrofit projects and legacy system integration. (The BE-OLS evaluation of Haystack is unavailable.)
Reference	https://project-haystack.org/
General Use Cases	Retrofitting legacy BMS, real-time sensor data annotation, equipment inventory management, semantic interoperability layer for SCADA systems, Smart Buildings, Building Automation, IoT, Facility Management, Digital Twins, Building equipment, control systems, sensors, actuators, HVAC components, and point-level metadata
Dependencies	Stand-alone. Haystack (in its available Turtle version) does not rely on any external ontologies, which is consistent with its intended design as a tagging and metadata model.
WILSON Relevance	Supports integration of legacy and proprietary building systems; enables semantic annotation of sensor data; useful for initial data harmonization in energy and maintenance use cases; complements formal ontologies like BRICK and IFC in hybrid architectures
WILSON Data Category	Sensor data, Energy management data

3.3.3. Semantic Sensor Network Ontology

The W3C-standardised¹ Semantic Sensor Network (SSN) Ontology (details in Table 9) provides a general framework for modelling sensors, observations, and sampling processes. It is frequently used in conjunction with the Sensor, Observation, Sample, Actuator (SOSA) ontology, which provides a lightweight version of SSN for easier deployment. SSN and SOSA allow for precise modelling of sensor metadata, including measurement units, accuracy, deployment context, and temporal validity [8]. WILSON uses these two complimentary ontologies to annotate and contextualise sensor data streams from various sources, ensuring semantic consistency across federated digital twins.

¹ <https://www.w3.org/standards/>

Table 9. Ontology Profile – SSN/SOSA

Category	Details	
Description	W3C-standardized ontology for modelling sensors, observations, and sampling processes. SOSA is a lightweight profile of SSN, suitable for IoT and real-time monitoring applications.	<p>BE-OLS Ontology Evaluation Graph</p>
Reference	http://www.w3.org/ns/ssn/	
General Use Cases	IoT, Smart Buildings, Environmental Monitoring, Digital Twins, Sensor data annotation, real-time monitoring, fault detection, environmental sensing, data provenance tracking, Sensors, actuators, observations, sampling, and actuation processes	
Dependencies	Dolce Ultralite Ontology (DUL), QUDT	
WILSON Relevance	Core for sensor data semantics; enables contextualization of real-time data streams; essential for energy and non-energy monitoring use cases	
WILSON Data Category	Sensor Data, Energy Management Data	

3.3.4. Digital Twin Construction Ontology

The Digital Twin Construction Ontology (DTC) has been developed to represent the construction phase in a project (details in Table 10). It can help with a vocabulary that describes the planning and design, status updates and generally the processes [9] [9]. DTC is well-aligned with other built environment domain ontologies and can be used in the WILSON project to automate the data-driven decision making and improve construction site to digital twin interoperability.

Table 10. Ontology Profile – DTC

Category	Details	
Description	a data model for representing and comparing project intent (as-planned, as-designed) with project status (as-performed, as-built) in Digital Twins of construction projects.	<p>BE-OLS Ontology Evaluation Graph</p>
Reference	https://dtc-ontology.cms.ed.tum.de/ontology/	

General Use Cases	Digital Twins, simulation models, Defect descriptions, construction management, construction scheduling, progress monitoring, process modelling
Dependencies	BEO, WGS84, BOT, GeoSPARQL
WILSON Relevance	Relevant to construction phase and process monitoring
WILSON Data Category	Building systems data

3.3.5. COGITO IoT Ontology

The COGITO IoT Ontology (IOT) is part of the COGITO ontology family, which includes seven well-aligned ontologies for various aspects of construction processes (details in Table 11). The namespace of the COGITO IoT Ontology is “IOT”, and it aims to model IoT devices as well as their measurement properties relevant to the construction use cases. This ontology suits WILSON uses cases for predictive maintenance and energy monitoring and optimisation, while can also support other use cases.

Table 11. Ontology Profile – IOT

Category	Details	
Description	COGITO IoT Ontology is designed to communicate IoT devices and measurements information. It is also aligned with SAREF.	<p>BE-OLS Ontology Evaluation Graph</p>
Reference	https://cogito.iot.linkeddata.es/def/iot/	
General Use Cases	IoT devices, Tags, Spatial Entities, Measurements, progress tracking, digital twin, tracking humans or equipment, monitoring, analytics, and decision support, real-time data integration, energy tracking	
Dependencies	SAREF, COGITO Facility Ontology (FACILITY), COGITO Resource Ontology (RESOURCE)	
WILSON Relevance	Supports lightweight, scalable modelling of digital twin instances; suitable for integration with WILSON’s Data Space connectors and data space brokers; enables real-time synchronization of building systems; complements formal ontologies (e.g., BRICK, IFC) in hybrid semantic architectures	
WILSON Data Category	Sensor Data, Energy Data Management, Building Systems Data	

3.3.6. Occupant Feedback Ontology

Occupant Feedback Ontology (OFO) is designed to facilitate semantic representation of occupant comfort feedback, which is often collected from smartphone apps or sensors (details in Table 12). It is designed to be used in conjunction of the built environment related ontologies and enable collection, assessment, and integration of feedback to improve user comfort [10]. OFO acts as a bridge between the qualitative feedback that an individual may have and its relation to a specific built environment element or zone. The Occupant Property Taxonomy (OPT) is a small taxonomic extension of OFO, where different types of comfort, contributing ambient factors, and human-comfort attributes are semantically categorised. The aim and scope of the OFO are quite in line with WILSON's energy-related use cases and pilot studies.

Table 12. Ontology Profile – OFO

Category	Details	
Description	OFO supports the semantic representation of both active and passive feedback, enabling comfort measurement, optimisation, and the linking of human feedback to corresponding physical features of interest.	<p>BE-OLS Ontology Evaluation Graph</p>
Reference	https://w3id.org/fofo#	
General Use Cases	Sensor data integration, feedback collection and transmission, connection of feedback to building features and elements, user-centric interventions	
Dependencies	Stand-alone, yet complements the classes and properties of the Building Performance Ontology (BPO) and Occupant Property Taxonomy (OPT) to enhance occupant-centric sensor- and energy-related semantic descriptions.	
WILSON Relevance	Relevant to user-centric feedback and satisfaction level collection, analysis, optimisation and overall discussion (for both residential and non-residential pilot sites)	
WILSON Data Category	User specific data	

3.4. Building-Level Ontologies

At the building level, ontologies seek to capture comprehensive information about entire structures, such as geometry, function, performance, and lifecycle stages. These building-level ontologies provide a foundation for semantic BIM and digital twin implementations.

3.4.1. Building Topology Ontology

The Building Topology Ontology (BOT) elaborates and details the spatial relationships between a built asset's elements such as elements, spaces, storeys, and buildings (details in Table 13). It provides topological representations by specifying logical containment, adjacency, and intersection relationships [11]. BOT is widely used for the semantic description of spaces and building elements in a building. It aligns well with BRICK and IfcOWL as well as many other built environment ontologies. Within WILSON, BOT will improve spatial reasoning capabilities in use cases such as occupancy patterns, emergency evacuation planning, and dynamic zoning for HVAC controls.

Table 13. Ontology Profile – BOT

Category	Details	
Description	Lightweight ontology for representing spatial and topological relationships in buildings, such as containment (e.g., room in floor) and adjacency (e.g., connected spaces).	<p>BE-OLS Ontology Evaluation Graph</p>
Reference	https://w3id.org/bot#	
WILSON Use Cases	Building topology: sites, buildings, storeys, spaces, and their spatial relationships, built assets' description, Space occupancy analysis, HVAC zoning, emergency evacuation planning, indoor positioning, semantic enrichment of BIM, Smart Buildings, Indoor Navigation, Space Management, Digital Twins	
Dependencies	Stand-alone. It has no dependencies with other domain ontologies. While not reusing any concepts from other ontologies, it is used by many other ontologies.	
WILSON Relevance	Critical for spatial reasoning in both energy (zoning) and non-energy (safety, comfort) use cases; supports federated queries across digital twins	
WILSON DATA CATEGORY	Building Systems Data, BIM Data, Point cloud model data	

3.4.2. Real Estate Core Ontology

The Real Estate Core (REC) Ontology aims to model and manage information about buildings, assets, and real estate portfolios (details in Table 14). It contains information about HVAC systems, sensors and therefore can also be used for facility management and EMS systems. REC aims to support smart building use cases and is designed to serve stakeholders such as property owners, suppliers, and integrators. It is highly aligned with the Brick ontology, and partially with Haystack, SAREF and BOT. REC is widely adopted for linking building asset data with real-time operational information, enabling interoperability across smart building platforms. Moreover, a Digital Twin Definition Language (DTD) version of REC

supports different graph formalisms beyond RDF. Overall, this highly aligned and modular ontology suits many use cases of the WILSON project.

Table 14. Ontology Profile – REC

Category	Details	
Description	REC is a modular ontology that covers Spatial modelling, Sensor readings, asset & HVAC modelling, tenant modelling, real-estate collections and events.	<p>BE-OLS Ontology Evaluation Graph</p>
Reference	https://github.com/RealEstateCore/REC?tab=readme-ov-file	
General Use Cases	Real estate management, Facility management, building management, portfolio description, Digital Twins, Smart Cities, HVAC and energy systems, asset description,	
Dependencies	BRICK	
WILSON Relevance	REC bridges BIM, IoT, and facility management data, directly supporting interoperability across WILSON data categories and use cases to enhance operational efficiency, asset and urban planning, and smart management of various systems.	
WILSON Data Category	Building systems data, Energy management data, User specific data, Maintenance & operations data	

3.4.3. Industry Foundation Classes (ifcOWL)

IfcOWL is the OWL representation of the Industry Foundation Classes (IFC), which is an ISO standard for BIM data exchange (details in Table 15). It can be made available for any version of the IFC schema, and it is in principle identical to the EXPRESS and XSD versions of the schema, including all features and (dis)advantages. The OWL version of IFC is particularly useful for leveraging the advantages of Semantic Web technologies, which allows effortless linking with other data sources (e.g. GIS), semantic querying and reasoning over BIM models. It facilitates complex interactions between building components, materials, and systems. Given its widespread use in the AECO industry, the IFC ontology is an important part of WILSON's integration strategy, serving as the primary ontology for semantic BIM models and enabling compliance with ISO 16739 and ISO 19650 standards.

Table 15. Ontology Profile – ifcOWL

Category	Details	
Description	Semantic Web representation of the Industry Foundation Classes (IFCs), enabling RDF/OWL-based reasoning over BIM data. Translates IFC EXPRESS schema into OWL for enhanced reasoning and querying.	<p>BE-OLS Ontology Evaluation Graph</p>
Reference	https://technical.buildingsmart.org/standards/ifc/ifc-formats/ifcowl/	
General Use Cases	Semantic BIM, automated code checking, clash detection, lifecycle data management, integration with IoT systems, BIM, AECO, Facility Management, Digital Twins, Full building lifecycle: design, construction, operation, and maintenance	
Dependencies	IFC (EXPRESS schema)	
WILSON Relevance	Foundational ontology for BIM data integration; core for semantic digital twins; enables data exchange WILSON Data Space connectors and PDH; High compatibility with BIM tools	
WILSON Data Categories	BIM Data, Building Systems Data, Maintenance & Operations Data	

3.4.4. Ontology for Managing Geometry

The Ontology for Managing Geometry (OMG) is developed to enable semantic description and exchange of the objects' geometry (details in Table 16). The OMG enables semantic representation of multiple geometric instances of a single object as well as the representation of its geometric evolution over time [12]. As such, it is an extremely useful ontology for comparison of geometry difference over time for retrofit or end-of-life scenarios. In the context of WILSON, it supports definition of geometry from heterogeneous sources or use-cases and can be compatible with BIM, digital twins, temporal monitoring of assets.

Table 16. Ontology Profile – OMG

Category	Details	
Description	The OMG ontology is design with classes such as Geometry and Geometry state, as well as properties such as isDerivedFromGeomertyState, which makes it possible for describing the state of	<p>BE-OLS Ontology Evaluation Graph</p>

	geometry besides the geometry itself.
Reference	https://github.com/tudallB/omg/blob/master/omg.ttl
General Use Cases	Semantic BIM, Point cloud data modelling; as-built; operation and maintenance tracking; visual tracking
Dependencies	SEAS, BOT, OMG, Ontology for Property Management (OPM)
WILSON Relevance	For managing and comparing geometric representations of buildings, elements and relevant objects; supporting geometry definitions from heterogenous sources; keeping multiple geometry states.
WILSON Data Categories	Point cloud model data

3.4.5. File Ontology for Geometry Formats

File Ontology for Geometry Formats (FOG) is a well-established ontology that supports geometrical descriptions and file formats in a semantic way (details in Table 17). With multiple properties for Point Cloud formats and some file formats for proprietary BIM authoring tools. Documentations have demonstrated that FOG works well with OMG and BOT ontologies and can handle both simple and complex representations together with them [13]. FOG is of great use for WILSON data category of point cloud. It helps with exchange of information where geometry formats are concerned.

Table 17. Ontology Profile – FOG

Category	Details	
Description	FOG is widely used due to its support of shapes and formats, as well as compatibility with different versions of IFC schema. It allows RDF-based geometry description.	<p>The graph is a triangle with three vertices. The top vertex is labeled 'Connectivity' and has a score of 3.0. The bottom-left vertex is labeled 'Reuse & Documentation' and has a score of 1.0. The bottom-right vertex is labeled 'Accessibility' and has a score of 1.0. The graph shows concentric lines representing scores from 0.5 to 3.0. The 'Connectivity' score is significantly higher than the other two.</p> <p>BE-OLS Ontology Evaluation Graph</p>
Reference	https://mathib.github.io/fog-ontology/	
General Use Cases	Semantic BIM, Scan to BIM use cases, definition of geometries and file formats	
Dependencies	OMG	
WILSON Relevance	Point cloud-based use cases; Geometry formats; RDF-based visualisations	
WILSON Data Categories	Point cloud model data	

3.5. District-Level Ontologies

District-level ontologies go beyond individual buildings to represent clusters or neighbourhoods, combining data from multiple buildings, infrastructure systems, and shared services. These ontologies are critical for urban energy planning, district heating and cooling systems, and resilience evaluations.

3.5.1. GEOSPARQL Ontology

GeoSPARQL is an RDF/OWL ontology (details in Table 18) and an Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) standard that provides both a data model and a query language for representing and reasoning about geospatial data in a Semantic Web context. It defines a formal vocabulary for spatial features, geometries, and topological relationships. The ontology can represent spatial entities at any scale, from individual buildings and infrastructure to entire urban regions.

GeoSPARQL enables consistent encoding, storage, and querying of spatial information from heterogeneous sources. It also performs spatial queries such as containment, intersection, or adjacency through extending SPARQL with geospatial vocabulary (ontology classes and properties) and spatial functions. SPARQL can query data semantically, while GeoSPARQL can query data semantically and spatially. In other words, GeoSPARQL builds on the SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language (SPARQL) by enabling spatial data representation and spatial reasoning within RDF graphs, turning SPARQL into a geographical query language. Within the WILSON project, GeoSPARQL provides the foundation for managing and linking all location-based information on a district scale.

Table 18. Ontology Profile – GeoSPARQL

Category	Details	
Description	GeoSPARQL is an RDF/OWL ontology and OGC standard that defines a data model and query language for representing and querying geospatial data on the Semantic Web. It provides classes, properties, and datatypes for spatial features, geometries, and topological relationships.	<p>BE-OLS Ontology Evaluation Graph</p>
Reference	https://opengeospatial.github.io/ogc-geosparql/geosparql11/	
General Use Cases	District level data querying, query spatial data (e.g. city models, infrastructure assets, environmental datasets), supports linking geospatial datasets, spatial reasoning in knowledge graphs	
Dependencies	Stand-alone. It has no dependencies with other domain ontologies.	
WILSON Relevance	Important for district- and city-scale digital twins; enables integration of heterogenous urban data sources and supports spatial reasoning or querying over geospatial data. It supports spatial reasoning, visualisation, and analysis for sustainable district management and policy decisions.	

WILSON Data Category	External Data
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3.5.2. OntoCityGML

CityGML 2.0 is a leading global standard for modelling, representing and exchanging 3D urban models, which is developed by OGC. It is widely used in geographical information systems (GIS) and urban planning applications. It specifies five levels of detail for modelling different urban features, including buildings, roads, vegetation, and water bodies. CityGML also supports semantic enrichment through Application Domain Extensions (ADEs), which enable the integration of energy consumption data, land use classifications, and accessibility information. In WILSON, the OntoCityGML ontology will be used to model the urban data in which digital twins operate (details in Table 19). Doing so allows for federated queries and multi-scale analyses.

CityGML is the original international standard by the OGC and is in XML/GML. OntoCityGML, on the other hand, is a semantic version of CityGML and is in OWL format [14]. Furthermore, a CityJSON version is also available, making the CityGML schema available in GML, JSON, and OWL formatting. As such, CityGML as a data model follows the same language-agnostic modelling strategy that also works for the IFC schema: a central data model is available, and several serialisations are available in different languages.

Table 19. Ontology Profile – OntoCityGML

Category	Details	
Description	OGC-standardised language for modelling, storing, and exchanging 3D city and urban models. Supports semantic and geometric representation of buildings, roads, vegetation, and infrastructure.	<p>BE-OLS Ontology Evaluation Graph</p>
Reference	https://cui.unige.ch/isi/onto/citygml2.0.owl	
General Use Cases	Urban energy simulation, solar potential analysis, flood risk modelling, district heating planning, digital twin federation at urban scale, Smart Cities, Urban Planning, Energy Districts, Climate Resilience, Urban-scale 3D modelling: buildings, terrain, city furniture, land use, and dynamic extensions (e.g., energy, noise)	
Dependencies	Stand-alone. It has no dependencies with other domain ontologies.	
WILSON Relevance	Key for district- and city-scale digital twins; supports energy planning and environmental analysis; enables integration of external urban data sources	
WILSON Data Category	External Data	

3.5.3. CityRDF

CityRDF is a semantic representation of CityGML 3.0, developed by the OGC to make 3D city models interoperable on the web. The content of CityRDF reflects the conceptual richness of CityGML 3.0 and includes urban entities such as buildings, terrain, transportation networks, vegetation, city furniture, and land use. Each city element is assigned a unique URI, enabling it to be referenced, queried, and linked to other datasets in accordance with Linked Data principles. CityRDF (details in Table 20) is the RDF/OWL transformation of CityGML 3.0, which succeeds CityGML 2.0. Consequently, it is more web-friendly and integration-oriented than OntoCityGML, due to its RDF-based design and updated concepts.

Table 20. Ontology Profile – CityRDF

Category	Details
Description	This ontology formalises the urban assets and components per definition of CityGML 3.0 standard by OGC. (The BE-OLS evaluation of CityRDF is unavailable.)
Reference	https://github.com/ogcincubator/cityrdf
General Use Cases	City Information Modelling, district management, urban development, infrastructure, building modelling, land use description, green spaces, public facilities
Dependencies	GeoSPARQL
WILSON Relevance	It enables semantic integration of building-level, infrastructure, and environmental datasets across different spatial and administrative boundaries. CityRDF supports cross-domain data exchange between energy systems, mobility networks, and built environment assets. It also property owners to have access to data and make better financial or investment decisions that are relevant to multiple WILSON use cases.
WILSON Data Category	External Data

Both OntoCityGML and CityRDF are semantic representations of the CityGML standard. OntoCityGML is a formal ontology enabling logical reasoning for CityGML 2.0, whereas CityRDF is a Linked Data vocabulary that serialises CityGML 3.0 for web-scale interoperability in digital-twin ecosystems.

3.6. Summary: Gaps and Challenges in Ontology Development and Use

The previous section gave a more detailed overview of the different ontologies that are available for reuse. The overview shows that they are capable of representing products, systems, buildings, and district information in sufficient detail for the WILSON goals. As this project aims to reuse existing ontologies as much as possible, we maintain the original list of ontologies that was provided (Table 21).

Table 21. Overview of Ontologies Selected for the WILSON goals.

Ontology	Domain Coverage	Alignment & Mapping	Documentation & Community
IFC	BIM/geometry	BOT, BRICK, SAREF	Extensive, maintained
BOT	Topology	IFC, BRICK	Active, lightweight
BRICK	Sensors/BAS	Haystack, IFC	ASHRAE, Growing, docs
SAREF (+extensions)	IoT/energy	SSN, BRICK, IFC	ETSI, standard
SSN/SOSA	Sensors	SAREF, BRICK	W3C, mature
Haystack	BAS/metadata	BRICK	Wide adoption, docs
REC	Asset/space	BRICK, IFC	Active, open source
BPO	Products	Schema.org, others	Research, mature
BEO	Built elements	IFC, BOT	Wide adoption, mature
OFO	Feedback	BOP	Research, some docs
OntoCityGML	3D city model	IFC	OGC, mature
GeoSPARQL	Geospatial	CityGML	OGC, mature
CityRDF	3D city model	CityGML	OGC, under development
FOG	BIM/Geometry	OMG	Wide adoption, mature
OMG	BIM/Geometry	BOT	Wide adoption, mature
IOT	IoT/Sensors	SAREF	Research, mature
DTC	Asset/Process	BEO, BOT, GeoSPARQL	Research, mature
MAT	BIM/materials	SAREF	Research, mature

From the overview and analysis, several gaps and challenges could also be recognized, hindering the full realisation of **an integrated ontological ecosystem for Digital Twins** in the built environment. One challenge refers to the **incoherent semantic granularity**. The existing discrepancies between the classes, properties, as well as conceptual coverage between different available ontologies, necessitate custom or domain-specific usage. Furthermore, the highly domain-specific needs of energy- and non-energy use cases within the built environment are **not yet fully or uniformly covered by available ontologies**, which risks fragmented, unaligned and ad-hoc extensions that complicate federation of data from heterogeneous sources.

The quality and maintenance of built environment-related ontologies further vary [6]. While prominent and well-established ontologies are well-maintained, updated and have thorough documentation, **others risk obsolescence or lack transparent governance**, which limits their long-term usability. While this document naturally excludes ontologies that are not FAIR, there is a multitude of ontologies developed and discussed in (scientific) publications that are never published and made available for reuse. These issues impact reuse and trust, and complicate maintenance or scalable reasoning across federated Digital Twins.

Distributed querying and semantic inference across loosely aligned ontologies in multi-actor Digital Twin ecosystems are computationally complex. When using the Vocabulary

Hub, **distributed querying can be time-consuming if the ontologies are too large**. One way to control this is to use modular ontologies (more like a network of well-aligned ontologies, such as those of the BIMERR or COGITO Horizon projects). This modularity of concepts for ontologies aids this by isolating complexity, the intrinsic heterogeneity of models' risks increasing integration effort and latency. Additionally, full web accessibility and FAIR compliance are not universally realised; many ontologies lack persistent web identifiers, open licensing, machine-actionable API interfaces, or comprehensive metadata [6], all of which constrain discovery, integration, and reuse, essential for dynamic data meshes such as those in IDSA or Gaia-X architectures.

Another significant challenge lies in the **gap between the rapid pace of technological innovation and the comparatively slower progress of formal standardisation**. Emerging topics such as green finance and sustainable investment, multi-hazard resilience modelling, and biodiversity impact assessment often lack semantic data models. This delay creates uncertainty regarding ontology stability and sector-wide interoperability, compelling practitioners to balance the risks of early adoption with the potential benefits of innovation. Furthermore, although automated ontology alignment tools have advanced, they remain insufficient to bridge semantic gaps in emerging and cross-domain areas. Expert validation is still required, extending development timelines and increasing implementation costs.

4. STANDARDISATION EFFORTS

The previous sections evaluated several ontologies for their suitability for reuse within the WILSON project, leading to a summary of ontologies selected for further use in this project (Table 21, Section 3.6). One key aspect deserves further attention, namely the level of standardisation that these ontologies have. **Standardisation** efforts are namely important for ensuring the compatibility of different ontologies and their use in real-world applications. While several standard ontologies exist, the main focus of this Section remains on those identified as most relevant to the aims and scope of the WILSON project, as defined in Section 3.6.

This Section will first clarify the **scope of standardisation** and why that matters for the WILSON project (Section 4.1). After that, standardisation efforts are discussed per category: **BIM, IoT, GIS**. Section 4.2 addresses BIM standards, focusing on the Industry Foundation Classes, ISO 19650 and Linked Building Data (LBD) (Section 4.2.1 - 4.2.3). Section 4.3 examines standards for IoT, including SSN and SOSA, ETSI NGSI-LD, OPC UA, BRICK and SAREF (Section 4.3.1-4.3.5). Section 4.4 briefly covers key geospatial standards, namely CityGML and GeoSPARQL. Section 4.5 finally gives a summary of this Section, including an updated table with selected ontologies according to the findings from the standardisation review.

4.1. The scope of standardisation

In the context of Digital Twin technologies and the built environment, standardisation is relevant for enabling semantic interoperability, data exchange, and long-term digital asset sustainability. Moreover, **making agreements among people** (= standardisation) is arguably much more important for interoperability than technology itself. Several Standardisation Development Organisations (SDOs) exist and have contributed to standardisation of various vocabularies, data, formats and procedures. Relevant to WILSON are **OGC's** spatial data standards, **ISO** or **CEN** standards for BIM and smart cities, **buildingSMART's** IFC standard and related services, and **W3C** recommendations for Linked Data and Semantic Web technologies. This section examines standardisation activities and their relevance to the WILSON framework with a focus on how these standards can be used to support semantic data integration, interoperability, and governance in federated Digital Twin ecosystems.

Note that the listed organisations define standards on European and international levels, which, therefore, have a very large scope and span. As a result, the corresponding ontologies have a similar wide span. It is important to acknowledge that, for WILSON interoperability, also standardisation (or mutual agreements) with a much narrower scope and basis are needed. This refers to **national standards, domain standards, company standards** and even **project standards**. WILSON explicitly leaves room for such standards, to enable **much more detailed and fine-grained interoperability and standardisation**. As part of the Data Spaces idea and concept, but also in the PDH, it is explicitly supported and included that **additional vocabularies and ontologies can be relied upon**, provided that they are made known to the WILSON tool ecosystem, e.g., through the Vocabulary Hub. Such level of interoperability is needed to be able to support data exchange properly for the demonstrator pilots considered and included in the project.

4.2. BIM Standards

The field of Building Information Modelling has seen a lot of standardisation efforts since its start, particularly under the driving lead of buildingSMART International. The most notable standardisation efforts are within the IFC standardisation context that has evolved significantly throughout the last two decades and more. More recent standardisation efforts took place in the creation of the ISO 19650 standards. This Section also discusses the notion of Linked Building Data (LBD), as those efforts took place under the umbrella of W3C standardisation efforts.

4.2.1. Industry Foundation Classes (IFC)

The **Industry Foundation Classes (IFC) standard** was initially developed and maintained by buildingSMART International. IFC is a key component of BIM data interoperability. In 2013, IFC was recognised and published as an ISO standard: **ISO 16739**, with the latest edition being updated in 2024.

IFC defines a comprehensive data schema for representing built assets' elements, properties, and relationships throughout their entire lifecycle. The IFC data model is not limited to only buildings, but also includes facilities and infrastructures (i.e., road, tunnel, bridge, etc). The IFC schema is widely used in the AECO sector for design, construction, operation and facility management. It is the de facto standard for exchanging data about the built world in an open and standardised manner.

The WILSON framework uses IFC as a **foundational schema** (EXPRESS, XSD, OWL) for semantic BIM models, allowing for alignment with ISO 23247-1 (Digital Twin Representation), ISO 19650 (Information Management using BIM) and ISO 16739-1 (IFC for data sharing). These standards place an emphasis on structured data exchange, information requirement classification, and standardised and transparent digital asset governance across project phases.

The ifcOWL ontology is the Semantic Web representation of IFC4 EXPRESS schema, allowing for integration with RDF-based systems and reasoning capabilities. IFC's compatibility with Semantic Web technologies makes it an essential component of the WILSON Vocabulary Hub, allowing for higher data harmonisation and cross-platform integration.

As indicated in Section 3.1.1, this report and project do not imply that an ontology requires the use of OWL as a singular language to encode it. In that sense, when referring to "**the IFC ontology**", this document refers to the IFC schema as a whole, whether it be in JSON, XML, EXPRESS, or OWL – all of which provide a formal and explicit representation of a shared conceptualization, according to the formal definition of an ontology outlined earlier in this document. The ifcOWL ontology refers specifically to the OWL version of IFC.

4.2.2. ISO 19650 Standards

The ISO 19650 series is a **six-part standardisation effort** that defines a framework for managing information throughout the lifecycle of construction projects and built assets

using BIM methodology. It establishes standardised workflows, information requirements, responsibilities and roles for stakeholders in project design and construction, as well as asset delivery, operation and end-of-life. ISO 19650 closely aligns with IFC, since it emphasises the importance of structured, interoperable data, formats and procedures.

As the most globally adopted and influential standard in the AECO domain, ISO 19650 series will guide WILSON's implementation of information modelling, exchange and delivery protocols, collaborative workflows and expectations, and information security and governance policies for Digital Twins. The ISO 19650 standards' emphasis on **information management** maturity and data quality assurance aligns with WILSON's goal of ensuring reliable, traceable, and reusable data assets.

4.2.3. Linked Building Data (LBD) standards

A third set of standards briefly discussed here, are the **Linked Building Data (LBD) standards**. LBD ontologies have been emerging since 2015-16 onwards, and they are typically associated with the **W3C Community Group on Linked Building Data**². While the number of ontologies associated under the LBD umbrella is potentially very large and includes ontologies such as BPO, BRICK, SAREF, Damage Topology Ontology (DOT), etc., a few primary ontologies can be named as particularly relevant in relation to the BIM standards illustrated in Section 4.2.1 and 4.2.2. These include the BOT, BEO, and MEP ontologies, as well as their relationship with 2D and 3D geometry representations. This set of ontologies is closely inspired by and aligned with the IFC ontology and covers a similar scope, namely representing core building information. These ontologies are not standardized under W3C, ISO, or CEN, yet are commonly accepted and referred to as standard in the building domain.

The **BOT ontology**³ describes the topology of a building, including its composition of interrelated spaces, storeys, and elements. This is entirely inspired and parallel to its implementation in IFC, and, therefore, the mapping between both is very straightforward. The concepts of containment, intersection, and adjacency are key to understanding the BOT ontology structure. Furthermore, the BOT ontology also allows to represent interfaces between BOT elements as well as BOT zones. Using interfaces, in principle, the interconnection between any two elements in the BOT ontology can be described, e.g., for heat transfer in walls and windows, navigation through doors and spaces, flow between pipes, and so forth. The BOT ontology allows any element to be associated with **a simple or complex 3D representation**. For this purpose, it is also strongly recommended to rely on the **FOG and OMG ontologies**.

Associated with the BOT ontology are the **BEO⁴ and MEP⁵ ontologies**. Both ontologies are taxonomies and direct counterparts of the **IFC Built Element** and the **IFC Distribution Element taxonomies** that are part of the IFC ontology. They enable the representation of walls, columns, sensors, actuators, doors, and several other classes that are key to

² <https://www.w3.org/community/lbd>

³ <https://w3c-lbd-cg.github.io/bot>

⁴ <https://pi.pauwel.be/voc/buildingelement>

⁵ <https://pi.pauwel.be/voc/distributionelement>

representing the physical components of a building. Several LBD tools and exporters easily combine these with the BOT ontology, thus enabling the representation of **BIM models as LBD graphs** close to the core idea of the IFC ontology.

4.3. IoT Standards

Over the past few years, several ISO standards have been updated or published that centre around IoT and Digital Twins, e.g., ISO 30712 and ISO 30173. These documents have curated terminologies and use cases pertinent to IoT and Digital Twins.

4.3.1. SSN and SOSA

The **Semantic Sensor Network (SSN) ontology**, standardised by the W3C, provides a formal model for describing sensors, observations, and sampling processes. It is often used in conjunction with the **Sensor, Observation, Sample, Actuator (SOSA)** ontology, a lightweight version that simplifies deployment in real-world applications. SSN/SOSA enables precise modelling of sensor metadata, including measurement units, accuracy, deployment context, and temporal validity.

In WILSON, SSN/SOSA will be used to annotate and contextualize **sensor data streams** from various sources, ensuring semantic consistency across federated Digital Twins. These ontologies will be integrated with BRICK and SAREF, and to a lesser extent Haystack, enabling seamless interoperability between IoT platforms and semantic data hubs.

4.3.2. ETSI NGSI-LD

ETSI is another SDO that has developed the new **Next Generation Services Interface – Linked Data (NGSI-LD)**, which is a standard for context information management, particularly relevant to smart cities and Digital Twin applications. NGSI-LD provides a JSON-LD data model and an API for representing and exchanging context data, supporting semantic enrichment and federated querying.

WILSON will use NGSI-LD **to implement semantic data brokers and context-aware services**, ensuring that Digital Twin models are dynamically updated with real-time sensor data. Its compatibility with RDF and SPARQL further supports integration with WILSON's Vocabulary Hub, the PDH and the connectors of the Data Space and PDH.

4.3.3. Open Platform Communications Unified Architecture (OPC UA)

OPC UA is a machine-to-machine communication protocol for **industrial automation**, increasingly adopted in building systems and Digital Twins. It supports secure, real-time data exchange and semantic modelling of devices and processes. OPC UA's information modelling capabilities allow for the integration of heterogeneous systems, including BMS, Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA), and IoT platforms.

In the WILSON project, OPC UA will serve as a **bridge between physical sensors and systems and semantic data models**, enabling real-time synchronization of Digital Twins. OPC UA's alignment with ISO 23247-1 and ISO 19650 ensures that WILSON's Digital Twin infrastructure

adheres to recognized best practices in data governance and lifecycle management with the built environment.

4.3.4. BRICK and ASHRAE 223p Ontologies

The **BRICK ontology**⁶ has been developed by the BRICK consortium as an open-source initiative aimed to “*standardize semantic descriptions of the physical, logical and virtual assets in buildings and the relationships between them*”. This ontology development has enjoyed strong industry support and is now commonly used by large BMS providers to enable the exchange of data related to building systems and sensor and actuation systems.

Currently, standardization efforts in this domain have moved towards the standardisation of the ASHRAE 223, particularly including the 223p ontology⁷. Considering its focus on building systems, its strong support by the industry, and its good standardization levels, the BRICK and 223p ontologies are important ontologies to include in WILSON.

4.3.5. Smart Appliances REFerence (SAREF) Ontology

The **SAREF ontology**, developed and standardised by ETSI, is designed for **smart devices and appliances**, particularly in the context of smart buildings and energy-efficient systems. SAREF provides a lightweight, extensible model for representing sensors, actuators, and control systems, making it suitable for integration into IoT-based monitoring and control platforms. The SAREF ontology scope is similar to the BRICK scope and an overlap between those ontologies is expected.

WILSON will adopt SAREF and its extensions (e.g., SAREF4BLDG) to support energy management use cases, including HVAC optimization, demand-side response, and occupant comfort monitoring. SAREF’s compatibility with NGSI-LD and BRICK further enhances its utility in WILSON’s semantic data architecture.

4.4. Geospatial Standards

Besides BIM standards and IoT standards, the WILSON project also relies on geospatial data, which also have strong standardisation levels, under the governance of the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC).

4.4.1. CityGML

CityGML is an open data model and XML-based format developed by the OGC for representing and exchanging 3D city and landscape models. Its standardisation efforts began in the mid-2000s to provide a consistent, interoperable framework for describing the **geometry, topology, semantics, and appearance of urban features**. The goal of these efforts is to ensure that 3D city models can be shared and integrated across different systems, applications, and domains, such as urban planning, simulation, and Digital Twin technologies.

⁶ <https://brickschema.org>

⁷ <https://open223.info>

CityGML is currently at **version 3.0**, and, as discussed earlier in Section 3.5, several efforts have contributed to creating also a JSON version and an OWL version of this schema / ontology. CityGML as a data model is highly relevant for the urban and district Digital Twinning included in its scope.

4.4.2. GeoSPARQL

GeoSPARQL is an OGC standard designed to enable the representation and querying of geospatial data within the Semantic Web. It was originally released in 2012, and it aimed to make geospatial data available for linked data and Semantic Web experts and applications. As such, its main goal was to make GIS data, typically present in GIS systems (e.g. QGIS, PostGIS, ArcGIS), available for Semantic Web applications.

As such, GeoSPARQL now defines a **standardized vocabulary for describing geometries and spatial relationships**, as well as a set of spatial query functions that **extend SPARQL**, allowing complex geospatial querying. GeoSPARQL is currently supported in most geospatial systems, and a key feature that is now enabled as a result, is that one can query for specific geospatial features, e.g., sites, houses, infrastructure, and their geospatial positioning in relation to other features (e.g., **nearby, within**).

GeoSPARQL is expected to be used in the **district Digital Twins** and the corresponding tools to be developed and supported within the WILSON project.

4.5. Summary

This Section reviewed different SDOs, their standards, and the ontologies that support or formalise those standards in machine-readable formats. Most of these efforts have focused on standardising data, formats and processes within their own domain or scope of interest. Hence, these efforts often remain siloed within their own domains, leading to **solid and reliable domain ontologies with a large-sized scope and span**. The section outlined the most standardised ontologies, which were already part of the list of selected ontologies in Section 3.6, hence these ontologies will have priority in further implementations in the WILSON ecosystem of tools. These key standard ontologies are marked in bold in Table 22.

Table 22. WILSON ontologies with the most standard ones marked.

Ontology	Domain Coverage	Alignment & Mapping	Documentation & Community
IFC	BIM/geometry	BOT, BRICK, SAREF	Extensive, maintained
BOT	Topology	IFC, BRICK	Active, lightweight
BRICK	Sensors/BAS	Haystack, IFC	ASHRAE, Growing, docs
SAREF (+extensions)	IoT/energy	SSN, BRICK, IFC	ETSI, standard
SSN/SOSA	Sensors	SAREF, BRICK	W3C, mature
Haystack	BAS/metadata	BRICK	Wide adoption, docs
REC	Asset/space	BRICK, IFC	Active, open source

Ontology	Domain Coverage	Alignment & Mapping	Documentation & Community
BPO	Products	Schema.org, others	Research, mature
BEO	Built elements	IFC, BOT	Wide adoption, mature
OFO	Feedback	BOP	Research, some docs
OntoCityGML	3D city model	IFC	OGC, mature
GeoSPARQL	Geospatial	CityGML	OGC, mature
CityRDF	3D city model	CityGML	OGC, under development
FOG	BIM/Geometry	OMG	Wide adoption, mature
OMG	BIM/Geometry	BOT	Wide adoption, mature
IOT	IoT/Sensors	SAREF	Research, mature
DTC	Asset/Process	BEO, BOT, GeoSPARQL	Research, mature
MAT	BIM/materials	SAREF	Research, mature

Of course, as indicated in Section 4.1, standardisation efforts not only refer to using the standard ontologies listed in the current Chapter, but also to **smaller-scale standardisation efforts**. While WILSON supports European and international standards, it explicitly supports also national standardisation efforts, company standards, and even project standards if need be. By enabling a narrower scope, **much more specific and detailed agreements** can be made between systems, which is typically needed in practice and can be **supported in the entire WILSON ecosystem of tools**.

As such, WILSON aims to balance formal semantic precision with practical implementation requirements. Industry adoption depends on demonstrable benefits such as reduced deployment costs, improved functionality, and enhanced interoperability. **Ontologies need to function in practice and align with the data and tool requirements in the field**. While large-scale standardisation may give guidance, this goal will also require standardisation and agreements on a smaller implementation scale (demonstrator-specific). Achieving this requires a closer collaboration between research communities and industry stakeholders, ensuring that the provided ontologies can support the requirements.

To be able to manage the multitude of ontologies properly, the WILSON project will rely on the implementation of a Vocabulary Hub, which is introduced in the next Section. The Vocabulary Hub aims to address the ontology management challenge by providing a mechanism for managing ontologies and ensuring semantic consistency across building-, district- and city-scale Digital Twins.

5. VOCABULARY HUB FOR WILSON ONTOLOGIES

As concluded in the last Section, the WILSON framework necessitates a systematic approach to **managing semantic data across multiple domains**, including building data, IoT data, building systems, energy management, maintenance, and urban-scale modelling. To address the semantic heterogeneity challenges outlined in previous sections and ensure semantic interoperability among diverse systems and stakeholders, a Vocabulary Hub can be used. A Vocabulary Hub is a standard component of a Data Space architecture and can thus also be supported in the WILSON data space. Furthermore, it can also be of use in the implementation of PDHs [15].

Section 5.1 explains the need for the Vocabulary Hub, outlining the role it plays in securing semantic consistency and interoperability. Section 5.2 documents the current implementation approach for the Vocabulary Hub in relation to the WILSON Data Space and PDH. Section 5.3 describes how ontologies are published in the Vocabulary Hub, as well as the processes needed for standardisation and access.

5.1. Need for a Vocabulary Hub

The number of ontologies relevant to energy- and non-energy uses cases of building or urban Digital Twins is high. As such, there are many domain ontologies and vocabularies for the built environment beyond those which are introduced in Section 3. Such **ontologies are commonly published on the Web and openly available using default web technologies** (i.e., HTTP dereferenceable URIs). In principle, a lot of vocabularies can be found directly in those host locations, and they need to be hosted primarily there as a single source of truth as well as ownership, according to commonly known Semantic Web guidelines and best practices⁸. If ontologies are not found using such best practices, and are, for example, only stored as a file in a Git repository, or not published at all, then they violate best practices and are not a primary reference for reuse. Most, if not all, of the ontologies listed in Section 3 are appropriately published.

If ontologies and vocabularies are properly published, and can be found using the openly available BE-OLS Ontology Look-up Service as well as the Linked Open Vocabularies⁹ (LOV) repositories, then **why would a Vocabulary Hub be needed?** First, a Vocabulary Hub can serve as a cache and fast retrieval mechanism for obtaining vocabularies in case connections drop. In that case, regular update of the ontologies in the hub should occur, to ensure that the vocabulary stays up to date with the source. Updating vocabularies to a next version does not happen often (once every year or few years), since ontologies are expected to be relatively stable to be adopted and (re)used. Second, more local ontologies, e.g., according to national standards, company standards, or similar, may also need to be supported, as argued in earlier Sections. In such case, a local Vocabulary Hub is a convenient way to extend the number of vocabularies at use, without necessarily having to go through a full publication procedure for the extended ontology.

⁸ <https://www.w3.org/TR/swbp-vocab-pub>

⁹ <https://lov.linkeddata.es/>

Thus, the WILSON project aims to support local ontology management by developing a Vocabulary Hub component. The Vocabulary Hub is of use for the WILSON Data Space as well as the Personalized Building Data Hubs (PDHs). At the time of writing, the implementation and novelty of the Vocabulary Hub is expected to be limited and directed only at enabling access to ontologies in local data exchange. In the implementation, directions and guidelines from the IDSA are to be followed. The Vocabulary Hub is an explicit part of the Data Spaces concept in its RAM4 architecture and is expected to have a counterpart in the new IDS RAM5 architecture model.

Aiming for an agile and limited implementation of the Vocabulary Hub, both for the WILSON Data Space and PDHs, Table 23 enumerates functionalities that are expected to be supported.

Table 23. Key Benefits of the Vocabulary Hub

Function	Description
Enabling the Use of Standardised Terminology	Ensures that terms and definitions are used consistently across use cases, reducing ambiguity and misinterpretation. The Vocabulary Hub allows stakeholders from various domains to have a conscious choice of the ontologies to be used and then a common semantic understanding, which is required for reliable data exchange and system integration.
Facilitating Ontology Reuse	Promotes the use and reuse of established, community-vetted ontologies such as BRICK, IFC, SAREF, and OntoCityGML.
Enhancing Semantic Interoperability	Provides shared, formal semantics to help with data harmonisation across multiple platforms and data sources. This enables advanced features like federated querying, cross-system reasoning, and contextualised data interpretation across the WILSON data space.
Supporting Federated Digital Twins	Allows semantic alignment of building Digital Twins and district- or city-scale Digital Twins. By standardising the metadata and relationships across these scales, the Vocabulary Hub contributes to WILSON's vision of a scalable, interoperable, and decentralised Digital Twin infrastructure.
Supporting Versioning	Follows and confirms governance and versioning methods that are commonly in place for ontology development and publication. Versioning happens with the producer of the ontology and hence is <i>not</i> a part of the Vocabulary Hub, but rather of the ontology editor's workflow. Only the (versioned) end result is published and made available through the Vocabulary Hub.

5.2. Implementation approach for the Vocabulary Hub

Within the WILSON Data Space and PDH, the Vocabulary Hub provides a central location for standardised vocabularies, taxonomies, schemas and ontologies. The current implementation approach for the Vocabulary Hub in WILSON follows the IDS Reference

Architecture Model (IDS-RAM 4)¹⁰. This architecture model recommends working with RDF-based vocabularies primarily. At the time of writing, the RAM5 documentation and technical interfaces are not yet publicly available. Therefore, the Vocabulary Hub design in WILSON remains aligned with RAM4 and will be updated to its RAM5 counterpart as soon as the specifications are released. Connecting the Vocabulary Hub to an Eclipse Dataspace Component (EDC) connector has been considered as a potential compatibility solution with RAM5. However, this approach would place the Vocabulary Hub outside the core data space environment, limiting its semantic integration capabilities. Therefore, WILSON will maintain the RAM4-based structure until RAM5 specifications are available, at which point the Vocabulary Hub will be adapted accordingly.

Although the Vocabulary Hub is not yet deployed as an operational service, it represents an important step toward a more mature and scalable WILSON data infrastructure. It should be understood as a preparatory and conceptual building block that demonstrates how vocabularies and ontologies can be harmonised within a federated data space.

5.3. Publishing ontologies in the Vocabulary Hub

The Vocabulary Hub component in the WILSON ecosystem is primarily used for accessing the standardised terminology that is part of various ontologies or taxonomies. This is primarily aimed at already available ontologies, such as the ones listed in Section 3. In such case, the main challenges for making these ontologies available in the Vocabulary Hub are to (1) ensure that the copied / cached version is updated with the latest version in the published ontology source (e.g., the URI of the BOT ontology), and (2) that the PDH and Data Space are able to retrieve this cached version of the ontology easily during operation.

So, although an ontology is, by definition, published through its own persistent URI, it may thus also be hosted and managed within the Vocabulary Hub. While ontologies are by default findable through their URIs, in line with the FAIR principles, they can additionally be viewed, discovered, and referenced through the Vocabulary Hub. In the IDS specifications, this activity is also referred to as “publishing.” However, the Vocabulary Hub does not republish the ontology under a new URI, nor does it modify its original licence. Instead, it provides a curated environment for referencing, managing, and maintaining access to existing ontologies.

As indicated, the Vocabulary Hub also aims to support publishing more fine-grained and more local ontologies, such as national standards ontologies, company-standard ontologies, and similar. For those ontologies, which are not expected to be default, a publication strategy and process is needed. It is expected that this procedure of governance and versioning is to take place outside of the Vocabulary Hub, and the Vocabulary Hub only supports making available the end result for WILSON tools. This aligns mainly with the ontology publication process explained in the IDS Reference Architecture Model 4 (IDS-RAM4), where it is the task of the data provider. The process involves data space building blocks, such as the Vocabulary Hub and the Metadata Broker. According to IDS-RAM4, publishing happens during the creation of a data offering. In fact, the data provider can

¹⁰ International Data Space - Reference Architecture Model v4 - [IDS Knowledge Base](#)

reuse already published ontologies or taxonomies instead of publishing custom new ontologies. Using already available ontologies encourages reuse and common understanding. Hence, this approach is strongly recommended and followed in the WILSON project.

Figure 1 demonstrates the processes and components concerning self-descriptions, vocabulary connectors and the Vocabulary Hub within a Data Space according to IDS-RAM4.

Figure 1. Vocabularies publishing process during the creation of a data asset. Process owned by data provider.

The main goal of publishing the vocabularies in the Vocabulary Hub is to comprehensively describe the data assets under offer. This description concerns both data and metadata of assets. It will be referred to only as data assets henceforth. This process sub-step is called Self-Description of the Data Assets. A well-described data asset helps the data consumers gain insights about the data structure, endpoints' descriptions and usage contracts before requesting the data. An understanding of the offered data asset helps in building Data Space connectors, which are the core components of the Data Space for information exchange.

Within the Data Space, the data provider and data consumer are the two main participants that interact through shared technical and semantic components designed to ensure secure, standardised, and interoperable data exchange. On one hand, the data provider contributes data assets via the Data Space. These assets are described using self-descriptions, which are published in the metadata broker and reference semantic definitions from the Vocabulary Hub. On the other hand, the data consumer interacts with the Data Space to discover available data assets. Through the metadata broker, the consumer queries the self-descriptions that refer to standardised terms and classes defined in the Vocabulary Hub. Therefore, the Vocabulary Hub serves as the semantic reference point of the data space by hosting and managing ontologies, taxonomies, and

controlled vocabularies that define the meaning of concepts, properties, and relationships used in the self-descriptions.

Thus, the ontologies reviewed in Section 3 can provide the formal structure and machine-readable semantics for describing data assets, enabling automated reasoning, validation, and linking of information across different domains and scales (for example, from building-level data to city-level Digital Twins). For data providers, the Vocabulary Hub ensures that their data is discoverable, understandable, and reusable across systems, while for data consumers, it enables meaningful interpretation and compatibility with their own systems. This implementation approach is followed for the WILSON Data Space, yet also for the WILSON PDH Implementation. It is not entirely clear what the future of the Vocabulary Hub will be in the IDS-RAM5. This improved architecture model will be followed as soon as it is available.

It is to be noted that the WILSON project uses different Data Space components for storing self-descriptions and vocabularies by following the “Separation of Concerns” principle in software system architectures. This principle refers to designing systems where each component handles a distinct responsibility, making the overall system easier to maintain, scale, and govern. For instance, all self-descriptions will be stored in the Metadata Broker, while vocabularies are stored in the Vocabulary Hub. This design choice reduces system complexity and organises governance, as vocabularies are less likely to be frequently updated in comparison to the self-descriptions.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The present report establishes the **semantic backbone** of the WILSON project by reviewing and collecting ontologies, vocabularies, and metadata schemas that enable a consistent and interoperable data representation across heterogeneous digital ecosystems. This foundation enables subsequent data integration, transformation, and pilot site deployments, based on which the WILSON architecture can remain scalable, reliable and interoperable.

6.1. Main contributions

This report describes the **selection, definition, and structuring of vocabularies and ontologies** for the WILSON ecosystem of tools. These ontologies, as repeated in Table 24, are expected to be used primarily in the WILSON Data Space and the Personalised Building Data Hubs (PDHs). The main contributions include identifying relevant semantic models that are aligned with the WILSON data categories in four levels: **material and product level, system and subsystem level, building level, and district level.**

Table 24. Final selection of ontologies for use in the WILSON ecosystem.

Ontology	Domain Coverage	Alignment & Mapping	Documentation & Community
IFC	BIM/geometry	BOT, BRICK, SAREF	Extensive, maintained
BOT	Topology	IFC, BRICK	Active, lightweight
BRICK	Sensors/BAS	Haystack, IFC	ASHRAE, Growing, docs
SAREF (+extensions)	IoT/energy	SSN, BRICK, IFC	ETSI, standard
SSN/SOSA	Sensors	SAREF, BRICK	W3C, mature
BEO	Built elements	IFC, BOT	Wide adoption, mature
OntoCityGML	3D city model	IFC	OGC, mature
GeoSPARQL	Geospatial	CityGML	OGC, mature
FOG	BIM/Geometry	OMG	Wide adoption, mature
OMG	BIM/Geometry	BOT	Wide adoption, mature

To complete the review of ontologies, **standardisation initiatives** in the AECO industry have been identified and listed, allowing to mark the most standardised ontologies in the list of selected ontologies (Table 24).

The last contribution of this Report is the explanation of how the listed ontologies can be included in the **Vocabulary Hub** as presented as part of the IDSA Reference Architecture Model (RAM). This Vocabulary Hub is indicated to be useful in the implementation of the PDHs. By providing ontologies through the Vocabulary Hub in WILSON, it is possible to enable consistent data representation and exchange. This includes the publication of custom ontologies, although the focus is on the use of ontologies that are standardised on a larger level.

These contributions lay **the semantic groundwork for interoperable data exchange**, facilitating subsequent tasks such as PDH development, connector implementation, and pilot site integration.

6.2. Future improvements

While this report establishes the foundation for semantic interoperability, additional refinements are planned in future work to improve coverage, usability, and alignment with emerging standards. Future enhancements will include aligning ontologies with WILSON use cases and pilots, optimising metadata schemas for performance and scalability, and discussion with relevant partners about the definition and implementation of Vocabulary Hub. Feedback from pilot site implementations and integration with other WILSON outputs will guide these improvements, ensuring that the semantic layer remains strong, adaptable, and supportive of project-wide interoperability goals.

REFERENCES

- [1] CEN, “EN 17632-1:2022, Building information modelling (BIM) – Semantic modelling and linking (SML) – Part 1: Generic modelling patterns,” 2022.
- [2] ISO/IEC, “ISO/IEC 30173:2023, Digital twin – Concepts and terminology,” International Organization for Standardization, Geneva, 2023.
- [3] T. R. Gruber, “A translation approach to portable ontology specifications,” *Knowledge acquisition*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 199–220, 1993.
- [4] P. Pauwels and K. McGlenn, *Buildings and Semantics – Data Models and Web Technologies for the Built Environment*, CRC Press, 2022.
- [5] P. Pauwels, S. Zhang and Y.-C. Lee, “Semantic web technologies in AEC industry: A literature overview,” *Automation in construction*, vol. 73, pp. 145–165, 2017.
- [6] A. Akbarieh, I. Osadcha, K. Farghaly, F. Bosché and R. Puust, “Development of a Built Environment Ontology Lookup Service (BE-OLS) with a New Ontology Evaluation,” in *2025 European Conference on Computing in Construction & 42nd CIB W78 Conference on IT in Construction*, 2025.
- [7] A. Wagner, W. Sprenger, C. Maurer, T. E. Kuhn and U. Rüppel, “Building product ontology: Core ontology for Linked Building Product Data,” *Automation in Construction*, p. 103927, 2022.
- [8] A. Haller, K. Janowicz, S. Cox, M. Lefrançois, K. Taylor, D. Le Phuoc, J. Lieberman, R. García-Castro, R. Atkinson and C. Stadler, “The SOSA/SSN Ontology: A Joint W3C and OGC Standard Specifying the Semantics of Sensors, Observations, Actuation, and Sampling,” *Semantic Web: – Interoperability, Usability, Applicability*, 2018.
- [9] J. Schlenger, T. Yeung, S. Vilgertshofer, J. Martinez, R. Sacks and A. Borrmann, “A Comprehensive Data Schema for Digital Twin Construction,” *29th EG-ICE International Workshop on Intelligent Computing in Engineering*, 2022.
- [10] A. Donkers, D. Yang and B. de Vries, “Creating occupant-centered digital twins using the Occupant Feedback Ontology implemented in a smartwatch app,” *Semantic Web – Interoperability, Usability, Applicability*, pp. 259–284, 2022.
- [11] M. H. Rasmussen, M. Lefrançois, G. F. Schneider and P. Pauwels, “BOT: The building topology ontology of the W3C linked building data group,” *Semantic Web*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 143–161, 2020.
- [12] A. Wagner, M. Bonduel, P. Pauwels and U. Rüppel, “Relating geometry descriptions to its derivatives on the web,” in *European Conference for Computing in Construction*, Dublin, 2019.
- [13] M. Bonduel, A. Wagner, P. Pauwels, M. Vergauwen and R. Klein, “Including widespread geometry formats in semantic graphs using RDF literals,” in *European Council on Computing in Construction*, Greece, 2019.
- [14] A. Chadzynski, N. Krdzavac, F. Farazi, M. Q. Lim, S. Li, A. Grisiute, P. Herthogs, A. v. Richthofen, S. Cairns and M. Kraft, “Semantic 3D City Database—An enabler for a dynamic geospatial knowledge graph,” *Energy and AI*, vol. 6, p. 100106, 2021.
- [15] A. Ramachandrani, R. Sharma, E. Petrova and P. Pauwels, “Vocabulary Hub for Semantic Data Exchange and Interoperability in an AECO Domain-Specific Dataspace,” in

European Conference on Computing in Construction & 42nd CIB W78 Conference on IT in Construction, 2025.

ANNEX I: Ontology Survey

WILSON: Ontology Survey T5.2

Ontology Survey and Analysis for Digital Twin Technologies and the Built Environment

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*Required

Survey Consent Form

This page outlines our ethical guidelines.
You must give your consent
at the bottom of the page
to start the questionnaire.

1. Introduction

Eindhoven Technical University (TU/e) invites you to participate in the “WILSON: Distributed Data Modelling and Federated Digital Twin for Lifecycle Data-driven Sustainable Operation and Management of Buildings and Districts” survey due to your expertise in digital twin technologies, BIM, semantic web, and ontologies.

Before you decide, please read the following information to understand what the study is about, what we expect from you and how we handle your personal data. After reading, you can accept the consent form. If you have any questions, please contact Dr. Ravi Sharma (r.sharma@tue.nl) or Dr. ir.-arch. Piter Pauwels (p.pauwels@tue.nl). You can also discuss this information with people you trust.

2. Purpose of the Study

This study is a collaboration between TU/e and several international partners as part of a Horizon European project. The purpose of this study is to analyse the role of ontologies in digital twin technologies for the built environment. Specifically, the study aims to:

- Assess familiarity with existing ontologies in digital twins, BIM, and building management systems.
- Identify challenges in ontology standardisation.
- Evaluate the potential of ontology use for data integration in smart buildings.

3. What Participation Involves

- Completing an online survey with multiple-choice and rating-scale questions on ontology use, challenges, and standardisation in the built environment.
- Your responses will remain anonymous and will be used for study purposes only. Except for your institution name, no other personal information will be collected

4. Risks and Confidentiality

- No risks are associated with participation, and your personal data will be securely stored and anonymised.
- Data will be kept for four years and may be used in follow-up studies or academic publications in anonymised form.

6. Stopping your participation

If you end your participation in the study we will not use your data anymore from that moment on.

For questions, ending your participation, or complaints, please contact the researcher through r.sharma@tue.nl or p.pauwels@tue.nl.

You have the right to request access, rectification, objection, erasure or adaptation of your personal data. Submit your request through privacy@tue.nl.

For concerns or questions about the handling of personal data e-mail the data protection officer of TU/e at dataprotectionofficer@tue.nl. You can also file a complaint with the Dutch data protection authority: the Autoriteit Persoonsgegevens.

7. Legal basis for processing your personal data

We process your personal data because it is part of the university's public task to conduct scientific research as stated in article 1.3 of the Dutch Wet Hoger onderwijs en Wetenschappelijk onderzoek. The TU/e always follows established codes of conduct for research integrity and the scientific standards.

8. Who has access to your personal data?

Only authorised employees involved in the study, including the researcher and supervisor, have access to your personal data, but only if necessary for their tasks. The authorised employees will keep your personal data confidential. Access to your personal data by third parties will not result in the sharing of your personal information, unless required by law. For processing your personal data in this study, we will use the services of the following parties:

- Storage solution: OneDrive
- Survey tool: MicroSoft Form
- Data analysis tool: Python, PowerBI and/or similar tools.

With these parties TU/e has a suitable agreement in place to ensure specific obligations to protect your personal data are followed. TU/e will process your personal data within the European Economic Area (EEA) by storing your personal data on a server inside the EEA.

9. How are your personal data protected?

TU/e has implemented appropriate technical and organizational measures to protect your personal data. These measures include using centrally managed and verified research and storage tools.

10. Confidentiality, storage of data and future research

The collected data will be stored on TU/e supported storage facilities that is OneDrive and ResearchDrive. This survey collects no personal data other than your institute name. We will ensure that any published research results do not contain confidential or identifiable information. We anonymise personal data for new purposes like research and education. We will ensure that the data cannot be linked to you, and we will not disclose any information that could identify you.

This study has been assessed and approved by the ethical committee of Eindhoven University of Technology.

By signing this consent form I acknowledge the following: *

Please select 2 options.

- I am sufficiently informed about the survey through a separate information sheet. I have read the information sheet and have had the opportunity to ask questions. These questions have been answered satisfactorily.
- I take part in this survey voluntarily. There is no explicit or implicit pressure for me to take part in this survey. It is clear to me that I can end participation in this survey at any

moment, without giving any reason. I do not have to answer a question if I do not wish to do so.

Organization *

Select your answer ▼

- CIRCE
- CSTB
- TUE
- RINA-C
- QUE
- PARQ
- WATTX
- ADD

Next

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General Information

Primary Area of Expertise in following data categories. *

(These data categories are as finalised in D 4.4)

- Sensor data
- Building systems data
- Energy management data
- User specific data
- Maintenance & operations data
- Point cloud model data
- BIM data
- External data
- Environmental data
- Financial/economic data

Secondary Area of Expertise in following data categories. *

(These data categories are as finalised in D 4.4)

Please select 3 options.

- Sensor data
- Building systems data
- Energy management data
- User specific data
- Maintenance & operations data
- Point cloud model data
- BIM data

- External data
- Environmental data
- Financial/economic data

Are you familiar with existing ontologies in the built environment and digital twin technologies? *

- Yes
- No

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Ontologies in the Built Environment and Digital Twin Technologies

Which of the following ontologies do you know? *

- BIMERR Ontology
- BRICK
- Building Element Ontology (BEO)
- Building Performance Ontology (BOP)
- Building Product Ontology (BPO)
- Building Topology Ontology (BOT)
- COGITO IoT Ontology (IOT)
- CityGML
- Damage Topology Ontology (DOT)
- Digital Building Ontology (DBO)
- Digital Twin Construction Ontology (DTC)
- Fire Safety Ontology (FISA)
- GeoSPARQL
- Haystack
- Industry Foundation Classes (ifcOWL)
- Material Performance Ontology (BPM)
- Occupant Feedback Ontology (OFO)
- Ontology for Property Management (OPM)
- RealEstateCore
- SAREF (Smart Appliances REference)
- Semantic Sensor Network Ontology (SSN)
- Sensor, Observation, Sample, and Actuator (SOSA) ontology
- SemanticBIM Ontology (SBIM)
- User Profile Ontology (UPO)
- oneM2M Base Ontology (ONEM2M)
- Others

Which of the following ontologies have you tried or used before? *

- BIMERR Ontology
- BRICK
- Building Element Ontology (BEO)
- Building Performance Ontology (BOP)
- Building Product Ontology (BPO)
- Building Topology Ontology (BOT)
- COGITO IoT Ontology (IOT)
- CityGML
- Damage Topology Ontology (DOT)
- Digital Building Ontology (DBO)
- Digital Twin Construction Ontology (DTC)
- Fire Safety Ontology (FISA)
- GeoSPARQL
- Haystack
- Industry Foundation Classes (ifcOWL)
- Material Performance Ontology (BPM)
- Occupant Feedback Ontology (OFO)
- Ontology for Property Management (OPM)
- RealEstateCore
- SAREF (Smart Appliances REference)
- Semantic Sensor Network Ontology (SSN)
- Sensor, Observation, Sample, and Actuator (SOSA) ontology
- SemanticBIM Ontology (SBIM)
- User Profile Ontology (UPO)
- oneM2M Base Ontology (ONEM2M)
- Others

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Ontologies in the Built Environment and Digital Twin Technologies

What are the main challenges you have encountered while using these ontologies?

Conceptual Challenges *

- Not Applicable - haven't used any ontologies before**
- I don't know what an ontology is – Lack of understanding of ontologies and their role.
- I don't see the purpose of using an ontology – Difficulty in grasping the benefits of ontologies.
- I don't know how the technology works – Lack of knowledge about ontology engineering and implementation.
- The ontology did not exactly match my needs – Misalignment between existing ontologies and specific requirements.

- It was difficult to extend the ontology – Challenges in adapting or modifying ontologies to fit new use cases.
- The ontology was too complex – Difficulty in understanding and working with extensive or highly detailed ontologies.
- Others

Availability and Discoverability Challenges *

- Not Applicable - haven't used any ontologies before**
- I could not find the ontology – Difficulty in locating an ontology relevant to the domain.
- No standard ontology exists for my domain – Lack of widely accepted ontologies in a specific field.
- Too many competing ontologies exist – Difficulty in choosing between multiple ontologies with similar scope.
- Others

Integration and Compatibility Challenges *

- Not Applicable - haven't used any ontologies before**
- It did not integrate with my current system – Compatibility issues with existing IT infrastructure.
- Ontology versions were inconsistent – Different versions of the same ontology causing conflicts.
- It was difficult to align with other ontologies – Problems in mapping and integrating multiple ontologies.
- It required excessive computational resources – High processing requirements for reasoning over the ontology.
- The ontology was not machine-readable or well-structured – Lack of proper formats (e.g., OWL, RDF) for automatic processing.
- Others

Data Representation and Encoding Challenges *

- Not Applicable - haven't used any ontologies before**
- I could not encode real-time sensor data – Limitations in handling dynamic, time-sensitive data.
- I could not encode geometry data – Challenges in representing spatial or 3D data.
- Ontology lacked support for uncertainty or fuzzy data – Inability to model probabilistic or uncertain information.
- It was difficult to annotate large datasets with the ontology – Scalability issues when applying the ontology to massive datasets.
- Others

Practical and Implementation Challenges *

- Not Applicable - haven't used any ontologies before**
- The ontology not complete – For our Usecase.

- It lacked proper documentation or examples – Difficulty in understanding and using the ontology due to poor documentation.
- The learning curve was too steep – Significant effort required to become proficient in using ontologies.
- Limited tool support for the ontology – Few or inadequate software tools for editing, reasoning, or querying the ontology.
- It was difficult to validate and verify the ontology – Challenges in ensuring correctness, consistency, and usability.
- Limited support from the ontology community – Lack of user forums, expert support, or active development.
- Others

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Ontologies in the Built Environment and Digital Twin Technologies

Rate the following characteristics of these ontologies

Semantic Alignment

Semantic alignment in the context of ontologies refers to the process of establishing correspondences between concepts, properties, and relationships across different ontologies. This alignment ensures that when different data models or domain-specific vocabularies are used, their elements can be mapped to one another in a way that preserves meaning and facilitates data exchange. *

	N/A	Unaligned	Minimally Aligned	Moderately Aligned	Strongly Aligned	Fully Aligned
BIMERR Ontology	○	○	○	○	○	○
BRICK	○	○	○	○	○	○
Building Element Ontology (BEO)	○	○	○	○	○	○
Building Performance Ontology (BOP)	○	○	○	○	○	○
Building Product Ontology (BPO)	○	○	○	○	○	○
Building Topology Ontology (BOT)	○	○	○	○	○	○
COGITO IoT Ontology (IOT)	○	○	○	○	○	○
CityGML	○	○	○	○	○	○
Damage Topology Ontology (DOT)	○	○	○	○	○	○
Digital Building Ontology (DBO)	○	○	○	○	○	○
Digital Twin Construction Ontology (DTC)	○	○	○	○	○	○
Fire Safety Ontology (FISA)	○	○	○	○	○	○
GeoSPARQL	○	○	○	○	○	○
Haystack	○	○	○	○	○	○
Industry Foundation Classes (ifcOWL)	○	○	○	○	○	○
Material Performance Ontology (BPM)	○	○	○	○	○	○
Occupant Feedback Ontology (OFO)	○	○	○	○	○	○
Ontology for Property Management (OPM)	○	○	○	○	○	○
RealEstateCore	○	○	○	○	○	○
SAREF (Smart Appliances REference)	○	○	○	○	○	○
Semantic Sensor Network Ontology (SSN)	○	○	○	○	○	○
Sensor, Observation, Sample, and Actuator (SOSA) ontology	○	○	○	○	○	○
SemanticBIM Ontology (SBIM)	○	○	○	○	○	○
User Profile Ontology (UPO)	○	○	○	○	○	○
oneM2M Base Ontology (ONEM2M)	○	○	○	○	○	○

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Standardisation Efforts

Are you aware of any standardisation efforts related to digital twins and the built environment? *

- Yes
 No

Which of the following standardisation efforts are you familiar with? *

- Not Applicable - haven't used any ontologies before**
 OPC UA (Unified Architecture)
 GAIA-X (data infrastructure framework)
 IFC (Industry Foundation Classes)
 ISO 23247-1 (Digital Twin Representation)
 ISO 19650 (Information Management using BIM)
 ETSI NGSI-LD (Next Generation Services Interface – Linked Data)
 IEEE 1451 Series (Standards for smart transducer eg. sensor or actuator)
 ISO/IEC 29192 (Focuses on lightweight cryptographic techniques)
 CoBie (Construction Operations Building Information Exchange)
 Others

To what extent do ontologies in the Built Environment follow to the previously mentioned standards? *

Not at all standardised

Highly standardise

Which of the following standards are most important for the standardisation of ontologies in the Built Environment? *

1	OPC UA (Unified Architecture)	↓ ↑
2	GAIA-X (data infrastructure framework)	↓ ↑
3	IFC (Industry Foundation Classes)	↓ ↑
4	ISO 23247-1 (Digital Twin Representation)	↓ ↑
5	ISO 19650 (Information Management using BIM)	↓ ↑
6	ETSI NGSI-LD (Next Generation Services Interface – Linked Data)	↓ ↑
7	IEEE 1451 Series (Standards for smart transducer eg. sensor or actuator)	↓ ↑
8	ISO/IEC 29192 (Focuses on lightweight cryptographic techniques)	↓ ↑
9	CoBie (Construction Operations Building Information Exchange)	↓ ↑

What gaps do you see in current standardization efforts? *

- Limited availability of well-documented
 Up-to-date ontology standards
 Lack of clear and user-friendly adoption guidelines

- Insufficient technical details and best practices for implementation
- Infrequent updates to reflect evolving technologies
- Limited support for cross-domain usage
- Inadequate governance frameworks for long-term sustainability
- Others

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Standardisation Efforts

Rate the following characteristics of these standardization efforts

Standards Compliance

Standards Compliance in the context of ontologies refers to the degree to which an ontology adheres to established technical, syntactic, and semantic standards. This includes using well-recognized languages and frameworks such as RDF (Resource Description Framework), OWL (Web Ontology Language), and SPARQL for querying, as well as following best practices in naming, structure, and documentation. *

	N/A	Non-Compliant	Partially Compliant	Moderately Compliant	Highly Compliant	Fully Compliant
BIMERR Ontology	○	○	○	○	○	○
BRICK	○	○	○	○	○	○
Building Element Ontology (BEO)	○	○	○	○	○	○
Building Performance Ontology (BOP)	○	○	○	○	○	○
Building Product Ontology (BPO)	○	○	○	○	○	○
Building Topology Ontology (BOT)	○	○	○	○	○	○
COGITO IoT Ontology (IOT)	○	○	○	○	○	○
CityGML	○	○	○	○	○	○
Damage Topology Ontology (DOT)	○	○	○	○	○	○
Digital Building Ontology (DBO)	○	○	○	○	○	○
Digital Twin Construction Ontology (DTC)	○	○	○	○	○	○
Fire Safety Ontology (FISA)	○	○	○	○	○	○
GeoSPARQL	○	○	○	○	○	○
Haystack	○	○	○	○	○	○
Industry Foundation Classes (ifcOWL)	○	○	○	○	○	○
Material Performance Ontology (BPM)	○	○	○	○	○	○
Occupant Feedback Ontology (OFO)	○	○	○	○	○	○
Ontology for Property Management (OPM)	○	○	○	○	○	○
RealEstateCore	○	○	○	○	○	○
SAREF (Smart Appliances REference)	○	○	○	○	○	○
Semantic Sensor Network Ontology (SSN)	○	○	○	○	○	○
Sensor, Observation, Sample, and Actuator (SOSA) ontology	○	○	○	○	○	○
SemanticBIM Ontology (SBIM)	○	○	○	○	○	○
User Profile Ontology (UPO)	○	○	○	○	○	○
oneM2M Base Ontology (ONEM2M)	○	○	○	○	○	○

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Future Directions and Recommendations

What areas do you think require further research and development in ontologies for digital twins and the built environment? *

- Real-time data integration
- Cross-domain interoperability
- Semantic enrichment of BIM models
- Standardization of ontologies for building systems
- Ontology-based data integration across platforms
- Enhancing ontology-based querying for smart building systems
- Standardization of Terminology
- Others

What recommendations would you provide to improve ontology development and standardization in this field? *

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Additional Comments

Do you have any additional comments or insights regarding ontologies and standardization in digital twin technologies and the built environment? *

You can print a copy of your answer after you submit

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ANNEX 2: Tool Support for Ontology Handling

To be able to work with OWL ontologies and RDF data, various tools and services exist that support processes ranging from authoring and management, to querying, inference, and integration. Table A lists these tools and provides an explanation of their main functionalities.

Table A. Overview of tools that support an ontology's life cycle

Tool	Description
Protégé	A visual authoring, structuring and browsing environment for ontologies. It is used to create, edit, and validate OWL and RDF vocabularies (i.e., classes, properties, and relationships), check logical consistency and visualise the model.
RDFLib Python Library	A Python library for working with RDF triples in Python. It allows to build, parse, serialise and query RDF graphs. RDFLib is helpful in automating tasks, such as reading, handling and writing RDF data.
SPARQL	A W3C standard that defines a semantic query language for retrieving and manipulating data stored in RDF graph databases. It can be regarded as the semantic equivalent of SQL, designed to manage and query data represented in RDF format.
SPARQL Endpoint	A query service capable of receiving and processing SPARQL queries for retrieving data from RDF graph databases. Such endpoint is equivalent to a regular SQL endpoint – part of a DBMS Database Management System, and is preferably shielded from unsecured and unauthenticated access by embedding it in software backends.
Apache Jena	An open-source Java framework for developing Semantic Web and Linked Data applications. It provides APIs for creating RDF graphs, storing them in triple stores (such as Fuseki) and performing reasoning and SPARQL querying at scale. It can be considered to be the Java equivalent of RDFLib in Python.
Apache Stanbol	An open-source, modular software stack comprising reusable components accessible via RESTful interfaces for semantic content management. It facilitates the automatic linking of data to ontology concepts, annotation of documents or datasets with semantic tags, and management of metadata within a content management environment.
FIWARE Context Broker (NGSI-LD)	An IoT integration tool used with ontologies such as SAREF4BLDG. It enables real-time data exchange by linking IoT devices, sensors, and digital twins with semantic identifiers, allowing dynamic context updates across systems.

The available tools supporting an ontology's lifecycle are not limited to those listed in Table A. For instance, tools relevant to the WILSON project also include Niagara Framework, SkySpark, Mango Automation, and Haystack Connectors. These are industrial automation platforms used for BMS. They enable the management and visualisation of operational data, apply the Haystack tagging system, and connect legacy systems with semantic models.

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